

**THE EXPLORE OF POSITIVE FEEDBACK ON EFL
STUDENTS' SPEAKING**

***EXPLORASI UMPAN BALIK POSITIF TERHADAP KEMAMPUAN
BERBICARA MAHASISWA DALAM PEMBELAJARAN BAHASA INGGRIS***

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**PROGRAM PASCASARJANA
UNIVERSITAS NEGERI MAKASSAR
2014**

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STUDENTS' SPEAKING**

Tesis

Sebagai Salah Satu Upaya Untuk Memperoleh Derajat
Megister

Program Studi
Pendidikan Bahasa
Konsentrasi Bahasa Inggris

Disusun dan Diajukan Oleh

MUH. ARIEF MUHSIN

Kepada

**PROGRAM PASCASARJANA
UNIVERSITAS NEGERI MAKASSAR
2014**

THESIS

**THE EXPLORE OF POSITIVE FEEDBACK ON EFL STUDENTS'
SPEAKING**

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Menyatakan bahwa tesis yang berjudul “The Explore of Positive Feedback on The Accuracy Of Efl Students” merupakan karya asli. Seluruh ide yang ada dalam tesis ini, kecuali yang saya nyatakan sebagai kutipan, merupakan ide yang saya susun sendiri. Selain itu, tidak ada bagian dari tesis ini yang telah saya gunakan sebelumnya untuk memperoleh gelar atau sertifikat akademik.

Jika pernyataan diatas terbukti sebaliknya, maka saya bersedia menerima sanksi yang ditetapkan oleh PPs Universitas Negeri Makassar.

Makassar, Tangga14 Juli 2014

ABSTRACT

MUH. ARIEF MUHSIN. *The Explore of Positive Feedback on EFL Students' Speaking*. (Supervised by Asfah Rahman and Kisman Salija)

The research aimed at (i) Finding out the effect of teacher error feedback minimizing the students' weakness in speaking English; (ii) finding out the student responses and perceptions toward the error feedback given in teaching speaking activity. The research applied quasi-experimental and exploratory study. In this study, one treatment groups and one control group are used. The treatment group received in different types of feedback, while the control group received no speaking feedback on their conversation.

The findings indicated that (i) the students' accuracy in speaking improved from poor to good category and the experimental class is higher than control class, the students speaking fluency has similarity because the comparison control class and experimental class showed that both improving the students speaking fluency, where experimental class is higher than control class, and the students' speaking compensability is leading to the ability to be understood or intelligible because the result of data analysis in experimental class for the students comprehensibility in speaking shown that teacher error feedback gave effect. The mean score of pre-test 4.45 and mean score of post-test 7.87. In control class showed means score of pre-test 3.38 and mean score for post-test 6.45. (ii) The students' response and perception for teacher error feedback indicated that students think their spoken error should be corrected when teaching language whatever English as foreign language and their errors usually to correct frequently, students also like very much if the timing the spoken error to be treated after finishing speaking, they also wanted their teacher focus more on their serious spoken errors than individual errors, the students responds shout treat their error generally strongly agree if their teacher gave them treat their error in speaking. They also was agree if their friends should treat their error, and the most popular corrective feedback in teaching speaking is explicit correction, elicitation, and repetition. They have effective function in detecting the students' mispronunciation and low accuracy and fluency. The other corrective feedback like implicit correction, recast, clarification request, and metalinguistic feedback are not favored because the percentage is lower than other corrective feedback. It is indicated that not all corrective feedback effective use in speaking, depend on the skill.

Key words: Feedback, teacher, speaking skill

ABSTRAK

MUH. ARIEF MUHSIN. *Ekplorasi Umpan Balik Positif Terhadap Kemampuan Berbicara Mahasiswa dalam Pembelajaran Bahasa Inggris.*

Penelitian ini bertujuan (i) untuk mengetahui pengaruh umpan balik guru dalam meminimalisir kesulitan mahasiswa dalam berbicara bahasa Inggris; (ii) mengetahui respon dan pendapat mahasiswa dalam memperoleh umpan balik yang diberikan oleh dosen dalam pembelajaran. Penelitian ini menggunakan *quasi experiment* dengan menggunakan satu kelas control dan satu kelas eksperimen. Kelas eksperimen menggunakan teori umpan balik dan kelas control menggunakan metode konvensional dengan presentasi, praktis, dan latihan.

Hasil penelitian ini menunjukkan (i) akurasi kemampuan berbicara mahasiswa meningkat dari kategori yang buruk ke kategori yang baik, kelancaran berbicara mahasiswa antara kelas control dan kelas eksperimen sama-sama meningkat. Kelas eksperimen menunjukkan bahwa hasil pembelajarannya lebih tinggi daripada kelas control baik akurasi, kelancaran, maupun pemahaman mahasiswa. Antara kelas eksperimen dan kelas control sama-sama menunjukkan peningkatan dimana rata-rata kelas eksperimen pada pre-test 4.45 dan 7.87 pada post-test. Untuk kelas control rata-ratanya 3.38 untuk pre-test dan 6.45 untuk post-test. (ii) Respon mahasiswa dengan umpan balik menunjukkan mereka menginginkan bahwa kesalahan berbahasa mereka harus dikoreksi dalam pembelajaran bahasa Inggris. Mahasiswa juga menginginkan selalu diperingatkan ketika berbuat kesalahan setelah pembelajaran. Mahasiswa juga setuju apabila kesalahan mereka dibenarkan oleh teman mereka. Jenis umpan balik yang paling sering digunakan adalah *explicit correction*, *elicitation*, dan *repetition*. Jenis umpan balik lainnya seperti *implicit correction*, *recast*, *clarification request*, dan *metalinguistic feedback* tidak sering digunakan. Hal ini menunjukkan tidak semua jenis umpan balik sering digunakan dalam pembelajaran berbicara.

Kata Kunci: Umpan Balik, Guru, dan Kemampuan Berbicara

PRAKATA

Penulis memanjatkan puji dan syukur ke hadirat Allah Swt, berkat rahmat dan hidayah-Nya sehingga penelitian dan penyusunan tesis dengan judul ” The Effect Of Teachers’ Error Feedback Of EFL Students’ Speaking” dapat diselesaikan dengan baik.

Proses penyelesaian tesis ini adalah salah satu perjuangan yang banyak menyita waktu dan tenaga bagi penulis. Selama proses penelitian dan penyusunan tesis ini, cukup banyak kendala yang dihadapi. Namun demikian, berkat keseriusan dan keihlasan pembimbing mengarahkan dan membimbing penulis sehingga penyusunan tesis ini dapat diselesaikan dengan baik. Oleh karena itu, penulis patut menyampaikan penghargaan dan ucapan terima kasih yang setinggi-tingginya kepada Prof. H. Muh. Asfah Rahman, M. Ed., Ph. D. dan Dr. Kisman Salija, M. Pd. selaku pembimbing. Ucapan terima kasih juga disampaikan kepada tim penguji, yaitu Prof. Dr. Haryanto, M. Pd., dan Dr. Nasiruddin Sainu, MA. Yang telah banyak memberikan masukan yang sangat berarti dalam penyusunan laporan penelitian ini. Ucapan terima kasih taklupa pula disampaikan kepada bapak Direktur Pascasarjana Universitas Negeri Makassar, Asisten Direktur I, Asisten Direktur II, dan Ketua Program Studi Pendidikan Bahasa Inggris, yang telah memberikan kemudahan kepada penulis, baik pada saat mengikuti perkuliahan, maupun pada saat pelaksanaan penelitian dan penyusunan laporan. Mudah-mudahan bantuan dan bimbingan yang diberikan selama penulis melaksanakan studi mendapat pahala dari Allah Swt.

Terimakasih penulis ucapkan kepada rekan-rekan di kelas D angkatan 2011, Dahlan, Aby, Trisna, ibu Rumaedah, Pak Nawfal. Ucapan terimakasih pula kepada teman-teman guru di SMK Muhammadiyah 2 Bontoala, adik-adik mahasiswa di Lembaga Kreativitas Mahasiswa Penelitian dan penalaran (LKIM-PENA) atas bantuannya, Bapak Rektor Unismuh Makassar yang telah memberikan izin penelitian, serta rekan-rekan lain yang tidak sempat saya sebut namanya satu persatu, yang telah meberikan masukan dan dorongan moril dalam perkuliahan dan penyusunan tesis ini.

Terwujudnya tesis ini juga atas doa, dorongan dan dukungan keluarga. Terkhusus ucapan terimakasih yang tak terhingga kepada Ibundaku Hj. Tanggi yang terus mendoakan jalan kehidupanku dan Ayahandaku Alm. H. Muhsin yang selalu menjadi inspirasi dalam mengarungi kehidupan, serta istri Musyarrifah dan anak-anakku Ilman, Ilmi, dan Faiq yang menjadi penyemangat dalam menyusun tesis ini.

Dan terakhir, penulis berharap semoga segala bantuan yang telah diberikan oleh berbagai pihak dapat bernilai ibadah dan memperoleh pehala disisi Allah Swt.

Makassar 2014

Muh. Arief Muhsin

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

A. Background

In teaching process, there are three main activities doing in every meeting. They are presentation, practice, and production. According to Pollard (2008) from the language point of view, presentation probably the most important aspect in studying a language, and finally teacher must give the students task to practice the point of the language subject and in the last activities the students should be producing the target language.

Like in speaking skill in teaching process, teacher has to know how to give as many opportunities as possible to speak in a supportive environment. Speaking is one of the most difficult aspects for student to develop because it requires them to produce the language most of the time, spontaneously without enough time to construct the appropriate and correct utterances (Pan, 2010: 5). It is possible because teaching English is a process where an aspect of English is connected to the student. The result of the process, for students can develop their speaking ability; aspects of the languages must be involved together. Due to a lack of English exposure in non-English speaking countries, most students do not have sufficient opportunity to improve their oral English proficiency.

According to Park (2012: 8):

“two of the most common teaching approaches are meaning-focused and form-focused. The former is communicative language teaching, it is based on the idea that a target language is acquired through communication and through direct instruction. This communicative approach places low emphasis on accuracy and gives more importance to the effectiveness of communication. The form-focused instruction involves the process of interlanguage construction by drawing students’ attention to providing opportunities to practice specific linguistic features”

English language teachers usually use authority to correct students’ errors, especially regarding the fact that students value and expect teachers’ feedback on their work. However, to most language teachers, giving feedback students’ speaking errors is one of the most frustrating tasks because it has more potential for subjectivity due to individual variables such as background knowledge, pronunciation, and spontaneity as influential parts. Therefore, the error feedback should be done appropriately; it will discourage them from practicing the language.

There are some argument that EFL students need to be consciously aware of the difference between what they are saying and what native speakers are saying before the students can modify their output. Good feedback puts the students’ form with the targeted language form; it is as an ideal position for the student to notice the gap about them (Pen, 2010, Ali, 2010, and Abedi, 2010). They argue that noticing the gap at a subconscious level does not lead the students to automatic correction, but this conscious awareness of the gap is a necessary first step for improvement.

Although a great deal of EFL learning takes place through exposure to comprehensible input, students may need feedback on errors when they are not able to discover the differences between their interlanguage and the target language. In other words, form-focused instruction induces students to pay conscious attention to forms in the input and thus aids interlanguage development.

Many studies have investigated teacher's preference for and the effectiveness feedback in EFL. Pan (2010:7) investigated the effect of teacher error feedback on the accuracy of EFL student writing. Ali (2005:9) investigated the effect of teachers' feedback on the students' ability to self-edit in 12 writing classes. Abedi (2010:10) investigated the effect of error correction versus error direction on Iranian pre-Intermediate EFL students writing achievement. Al Saeed (2010:5) investigated the effect of error correction types on grammatical accuracy in student essay revision. The entire researchers investigated the student writing class in giving error feedback.

Although many studies have investigated teachers' preferences for and the effectiveness of error feedback in EFL, relatively few studies have investigated the difference among teachers' and students' preferences for error correction. Also, to my knowledge, no studies have explored regardless of whether students' individual characteristics, especially anxiety, influence their preferences for corrective feedback. Besides that, when we read the articles that got, there wasn't one of article took speaking skill as the subject of the research. Because of that

true reason, the researcher tries doing investigation the error feedback of EFL speaking skill.

Although the students' errors are natural phenomena in the language classroom, it is quite difficult to figure out if the teachers should ignore or treat them. If the teachers decided to correct the errors, each one will be faced with these questions: which errors should be corrected? And how can teachers help the students to make the errors work for them? The answers to these questions are as complex as learning the language itself. It is even generally accepted that for the last two decades the language practitioners have different opinions on how to deal with the students' errors.

This assumption leads some people (such as Krashen and Truscott) to have believed that the negative feedback is unnecessary in language classrooms. Moreover, (Dekeyser (1993) in Johnson and Redmond, 2003) stated that error treatment did not improve the students' oral proficiency. The opposing view, on the other hand, believe that error correction is important in language classroom because some studies have shown that if the correction is given in the right way, it can improve the students' language skills. By providing the students with correction the students can learn which language item they need to work on and which feature they have made progress.

Knowing the function of feedback, the researcher interested to investigate the effectiveness of feedback in teaching and learning process. The researcher

did researching to know the students weakness in making error in speaking skill. The researcher used teacher error feedback to minimize the student problem in speaking.

The investigation did at Muhammadiyah University of Makassar in English department program. After the researcher did pre investigation, ungrammatical, mispronunciation and low accuracy are the main problem of the students. For example ungrammatical sentence, the student said “My mom love me so much, she giving me money every day”, other student also said “in the morning I am usually get up on 9 o'clock”. Besides that, some of the students still poor in pronunciation; like vegetable they said “vegetabl”, evening they said “evening” and some words of English they get difficultly to say. Some of the students also didn't know which need longer voice in the words and which need shorter voice is. In the other hand, the students have ability for speaking because they have rich in vocabularies. Generally, the students can speak while they at the class doing interaction. Even they can speak, more than half of them still make mistake especially in pronunciation.

Because of that problem, the researcher would do investigation to know the effectiveness of error feedback from teacher to the students while studying and teaching speaking process. The researcher tried to get out how are the teachers' error feedbacks in minimizing the students' mistake while speaking English.

B. Problem Statement

The present descriptive study aimed at analyzing teacher strategic management in giving error feedback. The main goal was to describe strategic used of feedback after the students doing of communicative activity in a specific context. The study raised the following research questions:

1. How were the effects of teacher's error feedback minimizing the students' weakness in speaking English comparing conventional method?
2. How were the student responses and perceptions toward the error feedback given by teacher in teaching speaking activity?

C. Objective of the Research

The purposes of the research were:

1. To find out the effect of teacher error feedback minimizing the students' weakness in speaking English.
2. To find out the student responses and perceptions toward the error feedback given in teaching speaking activity.

D. Significance of the Research

The study focused to find out the effect of error feedback to the students in teaching English speaking skill at Muhammadiyah University of Makassar. In the other hand, this research would measure the effect of feedback in helping the students to improve their ability in speaking.

The study hoped in positively contribution for education specifically in the process of setting and shaping students speaking ability. Identifying the student's perception toward the error feedback technique, this provided how the students could produce commentary feedbacks into their future revision in speaking. However knowing the perspective can influence the teaching process to make optimal outcome.

E. Scope of the Research

The study focused to investigate and find out the effect of teacher error feedback in teaching speaking skill. The teacher error feedback focused on speaking aspects like accuracy, fluency, and comprehension. It also investigated the students responses while teacher giving feedback in their error.

CHAPTER II

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Previous Related Finding

There were many researcher investigated about the feedback in teaching, they did the research almost the soft skills in English like writing, reading, listening and oral. Pan (2010) had investigated the teacher feedback on the accuracy of EFL student writing. He made conclusion in his research if teacher feedback had advanced the students in better linguistic knowledge and it develop improved accuracy the students writing with higher degree than beginner after receiving teacher error feedback. In the other hand, according to him, teacher error feedback was facilitated or harmful the students' ability to write accurately.

The next researcher doing researcher about teachers' feedback was done by Ali (2005:49). He had made conclusion the effect of different types of feedback on second language writing over the course of a year but found no significant difference on learner's essays with regard to linguistic accuracy. He also noted that to be effective, systematic training in writing required systematic correction of individual scripts and also indicated that the correction of student compositions is often ineffective in reducing errors because teachers correct mistakes inconsistently. Ali (2005: 55) gave recommendation if the future the researcher could investigate the questions posed in this study with larger samples and/or different methodology. Further research is also recommended that will take into considerations the

previously mentioned limitations and that will investigate factors that are most likely to be associated with teachers' use of feedback in ESL writing classes. These factors may have significance in the context of second of foreign language teaching.

According to Al Saeed(2010:60) who investigated the effect of error correction on grammatical accuracy in student essay revision, teacher feedback will always be an important topic for both teachers and students. Therefore researchers still need to investigate different feedback strategies to help students and teachers. The present study is a short termed and experimental study that has limitations, but it highlighted the possibility that some feedback strategies work better than others. However, it suggests that more research still needs to be done.

In the other research, Chu (2011) investigated; Effects of Teacher's Corrective Feedback on Accuracy in the Oral English of English-Majors College Students. He made conclusion if corrective feedback has a positive effect on improving oral English accuracy. Compared with score of experimental classes and control class in post –test, the score of experimental class obvious is higher than that of control class. Besides that according to Chu (20011), corrective feedback has a better effect on English accuracy. Corrective feedback does make great effect on oral accuracy, but the effectiveness for different level of learner is different. For medium and low group learners, the effectiveness is better, because there is enough space for them to be improved. For high group learners, their oral accuracy is better, what they need to do is improve their oral fluency and complexity.

In generally, researchers did investigation to analyze the students' ability in writing with experimental method. They was investigated the effect of the teacher feedback on the accuracy of the students' writing skill. There was no one investigated the relationship between the teacher feedback and the students speaking skill, and there was one used mix method in doing research.

After the researcher compared all the previous of related finding, he interests to investigate the effect of teacher feedback with the students' speaking performance. The researcher is going to try applying the teacher feedbacks in teaching speaking English. In the other hand, the researcher want to know also the students respond while teacher giving feedback to the students. The researcher will give description in explaining the data after doing investigation.

B. Theory of Error Feedback

When the teacher can give good oral error feedback strategies, it can boost the student motivation, advance language learning, and increase student perception of instructional effectiveness. We cannot deny also if the oral error feedback literature offers a confusing picture of what is appropriate feedback. Many teachers have heard that recasts a type of feedback that involves reformulating the student's error into the correct form, is an appropriate approach, especially because it may avoid increasing student anxiety.

1. The error

In general, errors have been viewed as language learners' speech that deviates from the model they are tried to master. The statement was supported by Park (2010:6), he made a distinction between mistakes and errors. He had used the term "errors" refer to systematic learner's errors underlying knowledge of the language. These errors display the learner's current developmental level of the target language. Besides that, the used term "mistakes" to refer to incorrect forms caused by memory lapses, slips of the tongue and other instances of performance errors. It is logical argued that foreign language learners can correct their own "mistakes" with assurance, but their "errors" are not amendable since their current linguistic developmental stage.

Researchers have categorized errors in various ways. According to Kazem (2005: 56) errors divide in two kind; global errors and local errors. Global errors refer to errors that significantly damage communication and those that affect from sentence organization, such as mistake word order, missing, wrong, or the place of sentence connectors. On the other problem, the affect of local errors single elements in a sentence but do not usually hinder communication significantly such as errors in noun and verb inflections, articles, and auxiliaries. Point out that correction for one global error clarifies the intended message more than the correction of several local errors.

From a slightly different perspective, Al Saeed (2010: 32) is categorized the errors firing from the strictly linguistic (phonological, morphological, syntactic) to subject matter content (factual and conceptual knowledge) and lexical items. Furthermore, the argued that high-frequency errors who made by students should be the first error for teacher should be correct in the classroom or another place that is suitable for them.

In the other argument, Mackey et al. (2000) errors will divide in four categorized their analysis of L2 interactional data. The four error types that had triggered the teacher using the feedback of corrective were phonology, morphosyntax, lexis, and semantics: (1) phonological errors were non-target-like pronunciation; (2) morphosyntactic errors were omitted plural *-s* and the preposition *in*; (3) lexical errors were inappropriate lexical items; (4) semantic errors were incorrect meanings or expressions. Some researchers also included a category that is relevant only to the specific target language. They have added logical argue because all of the types error is always come in teaching.

After we analysis of the theories, we can take précis if the error is of the important thing in teaching since they develop their linguistic stage. The error is come from the students' subject because every moment has different mistake.

2. The feedback

An article research was written by Łęska (2008), according to him the following definition of feedback *is information concerning the comprehension and reception of the speaker's message given by the listener*. Paul (2011) also was giving argument that feedback is the information will be fine by listener during a conversation. It shows our attitude towards the listener and influences their attitude towards us. Everything we perform and that gives some response to our listener can be considered feedback.

According to Paul (2011), to make decision for identify the error, it is resulting at least two important think from the attributes to an error feedback interaction. One is the identity of the error, which may be specifically pinpointed or left for the students to determine on their own. A second attribute is whether or not depend of feedback interaction explicitly identifies the fact that an error is made. Recasts, for instance, typically provide students a model of the correct form in a turn adjacent to their ill-formed utterance, and yet may offer no evidence that an error was committed. In case, the really complaints about recasts that they are confuse or difficult for learners to recognize as feedback (Lyster and Ranta, 2001:11) arise because the identification of the error may not be use of the interaction. Interpret recasts as implicit feedback and take prompts or elicitation for explicit, regardless of how teachers handle the error identification attribute, did not mention the support issues. Consequently, the recasts of Lyster and Ranta's (2001:12) study and those of Doughty and Varela's (2000:8) research is

not the same thing at all. As a result, one must be very careful when reading subject, the error feedback literature because it is difficult to know the true characteristics of error feedback categorized into convenient, but importantly types. Regardless of the research issue, the important takeaway is that teachers can increase and decrease explicitness via the identification attributes in feedback interactions, and by the one choice they make.

Ellis, et al (2006: 33) consist this attribute important, designed recasting their study that clearly about the errors. There are two causes to consider regarding error identity: (a) knowing students that an error was made, and (b) drawing their attention to the exact nature of the error. The more important that teachers should focus on doing this identification, the more students will notice the error feedback, and the more explicit the feedback becomes. Explicit versus implicit feedback is an area that has knowing much research interest.

The typical of the feedback approach, however, has unfortunately obscured inquiry in this area (Margollis, 2007:26). For example, researchers tend to the main good of this attributes model is that it highlights choices available to teachers that allow them to give feedback for the specific needs in learning process. For students who demonstrate a great degree of anxiety and discomfort about oral error feedback, for instance, teachers might provide recasts or prompts with little or no identification of the error. While for students who possess

confidence, teachers might more boldly identify the fact an error was committed and, possibly, the specific nature of the error.

Figure 1. Error Feedback Attributes Model

Figure 1. Error Feedback Attributes Model

The main point of considering feedback from an attributes model rather than a feedback type approach comes in the recognition of more decision points to fine oral error feedback to individual learner needs. After knowing with the case issue, teachers can focus on repair. Repairs, like the identification attribute, include at least two options: (a) providing input, or a correct model, and (b) requiring student modified output, or production (Margolis, 2007: 35). As with the identification case the teacher could use neither, one, or both. If repair is undertaken, the goal is fixed the form, which students may confuse for explicitly notice. Recasts are the quintessential example of how teacher provide repair with

input. The argument of students to modify their utterance, with confirmation checks, comprehension questions, or via repetition is an alternative to recasts. Sometimes the Teachers use both techniques in the same error feedback interaction.

The final points of the problem in this Error Feedback Attributes Model regard providing support for the learning that potentially occurred during the feedback interaction. This support could be seen as schema building that is, helping learners connect the new information to what they already know. One way is through fine-tuning (Han, 2001), explaining, for example, that modals never take tense and do not act like other verbs. Attention activities, such as error feedback case or revisiting an error at a later time might also support student learning.

These three decision important points offer opportunities to teachers; start from the opening error feedback interactions to a variety of unique attributes, avoiding the one size fits all limitations of feedback type models. The model also recognizes that time itself is an important think to consider. Feedback can know or delayed. It can also be a brief interaction or a lengthy one. Adding these attributes and three sets of decisions to the error feedback repertoire expands the ability of teachers to provide meaningful feedback to oral errors.

3. Types of feedback

A various operationalized definitions of corrective feedback have been used of the Researchers, and Kazem (2005:82) define the term feedback correction

as the replacement of error or mistake by what is correct. The correction is given when the speaker explains the action and listener is given reaction. Sun at all (2010:4) defined correction as any reaction of the teacher which clearly transforms, disapprovingly refers to or demands improvement of the learner's correlation, which is the most common conception employed by researchers.

Lightbown and Spada (1999:171) define corrective feedback as any indication to the learners that their use of the target language is incorrect. Corrective feedback includes both explicit and implicit feedback. Teachers can provide corrective feedback either without interrupting the flow of conversation (implicit feedback) or overtly with an emphasis on the ill-formed utterance (explicit feedback).

Long and Robinson (1998:23) make a statement between negative and positive feedback: negative points of feedback is out to the learners that their utterances are faulty in some way, and all feedback that is not negative is positive. Long (1996:429) defines negative feedback as giving correction by following an ungrammatical learner system. Long claimed that negative feedback is generally facilitative of L2 acquisition and Foreign Language acquisition because negative feedback, such as recasts, contains positive evidence, which provides the correct form.

Lyster & Ranta (2001:67) developed six types of feedback used by teachers in response to learner errors:

1. *Explicit correction* refers to the explicit provision of the correct form. As the teacher provides the correct form, he or she clearly indicates that what the student said is incorrect (e.g., “Oh, you mean,” “You should say”).
2. *Recasts* involve the teacher’s reformulation of all or part of a student’s utterance, minus the error.
3. *Clarification requests* indicate to students either that their utterance has not been understood by the teacher or that the utterance is ill-formed in some way and that a repetition or a reformulation is required. A clarification request includes phrases such as “Pardon me?”
4. *Metalinguistic feedback* contains comments, information, or questions related to the well-formedness of the student’s utterance, without explicitly providing the correct form (e.g., “Can you find your error?”).
5. *Elicitation* refers to a technique that teachers use to directly elicit the correct form from the student. Teachers elicit completion of their own utterance by strategically pausing to allow students to “fill in the blank.”
6. *Repetition* refers to the teacher’s repetition, in isolation, of the student’s erroneous utterance. In most cases, teachers adjust their intonation so as to highlight the error.

After we knew some case of feedback according to the researcher, models of Lyster and Ranta is agree used by teacher to give feedback for the student. This model will be used to do investigation in this research.

4. Teachers' and students' preferences for error correction

Akew (2001) announcement that teachers need to know learners' beliefs about language learning in order to make effective learning strategies in their students because severe disappointment caused by using a mismatch between students' information about language learning and the realities they encounter in the classroom can impede language acquisition. Researchers have investigated teachers' and students' argument of error correction and found mismatches between them.

On the other hand, Schulz's (2001: 349) studies said that students' attitudes toward grammar instruction and error correction were more gratify than their teachers' attitudes; that is, learners want more error correction. Thus, when their instructional expectations are not met, their motivation can be down and they may question the quality of the teacher. His argued that such lack of pedagogical face validity could affect learners' motivation. The discrepancies between students' and teachers' expectations can make negatively affect L2 students' satisfaction with the language class and can potentially lead to the discontinuation of L2 study. Teachers, therefore, need to explore their students'

perceptions and expectations to close the gap and maximize the effects of teaching.

Ancker's (2000:5) investigated for the action research teachers' and students' expectations toward error correction by surveying teachers and students in 15 countries. The survey asked whether teachers should correct every error students make when using English. Interestingly, the findings showed a big gap between the teachers and the students. For example, when the students and teachers were make communication whether teachers should correct every error students make when using English, only 25% of teachers answered "yes" while 76% of students answered "yes." The most frequent reason given for not wanting correction was the negative impact of correction on students' self confidence and good motivation, whereas the most important reason given for wanting correction was the importance of learning to speak English correctly. Ancker suggests that to close the different between teachers' and learners' expectations, teachers should make clear objectives in lesson plans, discuss the learning process with students, and give alternative types of corrective feedback that can be effective and encouraging to students.

Yoshida (2008:12) researches that teachers' and learners' preferences for corrective feedback types in Japanese classrooms through audio recording and stimulated recall interviews with participants. The findings showed that recasts were the teachers' most favored corrective feedback type over elicitation and metalinguistic feedback due to the time limitation of classes and their awareness

of learners' cognitive styles. On the contrary, the learners may have an opportunity to think about their errors in problem to fine up with the correct forms before receiving correct feedback from their teachers.

Fukuda (2004:10) investigated teachers' and students' statements about error treatment by using survey for teachers and students in Japanese high school oral communication classes. The results of the survey revealed significant differences between the teachers and students regarding error treatment. Overall, the students wanted more error treatment than their teachers believed. Based on the findings, Fukuda suggested that the effective error treatment is extremely complex since it comes from many factors, one of them students' needs, preferences, personalities, proficiency levels, and motivation.

After we compared some researcher findings, we can make conclusion if foreign language teachers should check their students' perspectives and discuss the rationale in and behind the instructional strategies. They have to support each other to get many various suitable conditions in teaching.

C. Teaching Speaking

Shortage of opportunities for practice is identified as an important contributing factor to speaking subject. And by practice is meant, not practice in grammar and vocabulary, but practice in interactive and meaningful speaking itself.

According with the communicative statement, and the sociocultural theory, all learning - including the learning of a foreign language - is mediated through social and cultural activity (Park, 2010: 28). To fine autonomy in a skill, the learner first needs to experience other-regulation, that is, the mediation of a “better other”. This typically takes the form of assisted performance, as the teacher instruction with the learner to provide a supportive framework within the learners can extend their present competence. According this shared activity, new knowledge is constructed until the learners are in a position to appropriate it. At this stage the scaffolding can be gradually dismantled. Learners are now able to function independently is a state of self-regulation.

That is, learning, as seen through this theory, is fundamentally a social phenomenon, requiring both activity and interactivity (Alqahtani at all, 2011: 7). In classroom terms, it takes place in cycles of assisted performance, in which learning is collaborative, co-constructed, and scaffold.

According to Alqahtani at all, (2011: 9) was giving for the speaking opportunities and increasing the chances that students will be experienced autonomous language use, any situations need to be met:

1. *Productivity* - a speaking problem needs to be maximally language productive in order to provide the best conditions for autonomous language use. If students can do a task by simply exchanging isolated words, or if only a couple of students participate in a group discussion, the task may not justify the time spent on it.

2. *Purposefulness* – the good Language can be increased by making sure the speaking activity has a clear outcome, especially one which requires learners to work together to achieve a common purpose.
3. *Interactivity* - activities should require learners to take into account the effect they are having on their audience. There should be a real person present, one which can demonstrate interest, understanding, and even ask questions or make comments.
4. *Challenge* - the task should stretch the learners so that they are forced to draw on their available communicative resources to achieve the outcome. This will help them to experience the sense of achievement that is part of autonomous language use. But if the degree of challenge is too high, this can be counterproductive, inhibiting learners or reducing them to speaking in their L1. The teacher needs to be sensitive to the degree of difficulty a task presents individual learners and to adjust it accordingly.
5. *Safety* – in learning process should be attention they also need to feel confident that, when meeting those challenges and attempting autonomous language use, they can do so without too much risk. The classroom should be good conditions for experimentation, including a situation of classroom dynamic and a non-judgmental attitude to errors. Also, learners need to be known in the knowledge that the teacher will always be there to guide and support them in their learning process.

6. *Authenticity* - speaking tasks should have some relation to real-life language use. Learners will need to experience a quality of communication in the classroom that is essentially the same as communication outside the classroom. This means that they will need to perform in real operating conditions. It also means that the kind of topics, genres and situations that are selected for speaking tasks bear some relation to the learners' perceived needs and interests.

Speaking skill is an important part of the curriculum in teaching a language, and this is made it an important object of assessment as well. Assessing speaking test is challenging, because there are so many factors that must be considering which influence our impression of how well somebody can produce speaking in a language, and because we hope test scores can be accurate, only and appropriate for our goal.

In the other opinion, according to Case (2008) speaking feedback is information a teacher or another speaker, including another learner, gives to learners on how well they are doing, either to help the learner improve specific points, or to help plan their learning. Feedback can be immediate, during an activity, or delayed, at the end of an activity or part of learning programmed and can take various forms. He was classified fifteen ways to correct speaking errors, the ways are:

1. Collect the errors for later

We can then correct them later in the same class (with a game like a grammar auction or just eliciting corrections from the class) or in a future class (for example writing error dictation pair work worksheets or using the same techniques as can be used in the same class). Make sure we give positive reinforcement as well.

2. Facial expression

For example, raise an eyebrow, tilt our head to one side or give a slight frown. Most people will do this naturally, but there is a slight chance a teacher's expression will be too critical or too subtle for our students to pick up on, and we can (amusingly) practice facial expressions in a teaching workshop by participants communicating certain typical classroom messages ("move over there to work with this person", "work in pairs" etc.) using just their heads and faces, including feedback on spoken errors in that list.

3. Body language

The problems with using body language to show errors could also be that it is taken as very serious criticism or that it is too vague. Possibilities include using our hands (rolling a hand from side to side to mean "so-so attempt"; making a circle by moving our index finger to mean "one more time"; or a cross with fingers, open palms or even forearms to show a very clear "no" or "wrong"- probably only suitable for a team game etc where the responsibility is shared), head (tilted to one side to mean "I'm not sure that sounds correct"),

or shoulders (hunched to reinforce “I don’t understand what you are saying”). Again, practicing this in a teaching workshop can be useful, as can eliciting other body language teachers could have used after an observation.

4. Point at the correct language

If we have something on the correct form easily accessible on the whiteboard, in the textbook or on a poster, just pointing at it can be a subtle but clear way of prompting students to use the correct language. What we point at could be the name of the tense or word form they are supposed to be using, a verb forms table or the actual correct verb form, a grammatical explanation, or another grammatical hint such as “future”, “prediction” or “polite”.

5. Repeat what they said

This can mean repeating the whole sentence, one section of it including the wrong part, the sentence up to the wrong part, the sentence with the wrong part missed out (with maybe a humming noise to show the gap that should be filled) or just the wrong part. We can illustrate that we are showing them an error and give some hint as to which bit is wrong by using a questioning tone (for everything you say or just for the wrong part). This method is overused by some teachers and can sound patronizing if used too often or with the wrong tone of voice, so try to mix up the different versions of it described here and to alternate with methods described in the other tips.

6. Just say the right version

The students can then repeat the correct version or tell us what the difference between the two sentences was and why their version was wrong. Because the students don't do much of the work in this way of being corrected, it might not be as good a way of remembering the correction as methods where we give more subtle clues. Its advantages are that it is quick and suits cultures, classes and students that think of elicitation as shirking by the teacher. It can also be more face-saving than asking them for self-correction, as trying to correct themselves risks making even more mistakes. The "right version" could mean the whole sentence or just the correction of the part that was wrong. In the latter case, we can then ask them to put it into the sentence in the right place and repeat the whole thing.

7. Tell them how many mistakes

This method is only really suitable for controlled speaking practice, but can be a very simple way of giving feedback in that situation. Examples include "Most of the comparatives were right, but we made two mistakes" and "Three words are in the wrong position in the sentence/ are mixed up". Make sure we only use this method when students can remember what we are referring to without too much prompting.

8. Use grammatical terminology to identify the mistake

For example, "(You used) the wrong tense", "Not the Present Perfect", "You need an adverb, not an adjective" or "Can change that into the passive/

indirect speech?” This method is perhaps overused, and we need to be sure that the grammatical terminology isn’t just going to confuse them more.

9. Give the rule

For example, “‘Since’ usually takes the Present Perfect” or “One syllable adjectives make the comparative with –er, not more + adjective” This works best if they already know the rule, and ywe at least need to make sure that they will quickly understand what we are saying, for example by only using grammatical terminology we have used with them several times before.

10. Give a number of points

This is probably best saved for part of a game, especially one where students work together, but we can give each response a number of points out of 10. The same or other teams can then make another attempt at saying the same thing to see if they can get more points. If we don’t want students to focus on accuracy too much, tell them that the points will also give them credit for good pronunciation, fluency, politeness, persuasiveness and/ or originality of ideas.

11. Just tell them they are wrong (but nicely)

Positive ways of being negative include “nearly there”, “getting closer”, “just one mistake”, “much better”, “good idea, but...”, “I understand what you mean but...”, “you have made a mistake that almost everyone does/ that’s a very common mistake”, “we haven’t studied this yet, but...” and “much better pronunciation, but...” With lower level and new classes, we might have to

balance the need to be nice with the need to be clear and not confuse them with feedback language that they don't understand, perhaps by sticking to one or two phrases to give feedback for the first couple of months. It can also be useful to give them translations of this and other classroom language we will use, for example on a worksheet or a poster.

12. Tell them what part they should change

For example, "You need to change the introduction to your presentation" or "Try replacing the third word with something else"

13. Ask partners to spot errors

This is a fairly well-known way of giving feedback in speaking tasks, but it can be a minefield if the person giving feedback has no confidence in their ability to do so or in how well the feedback (i.e. criticism) will be taken, and even more so if the person receiving the feedback will in fact react badly. This method is easier to do and easier to take when they have been told specifically which language to use while speaking and so to look out for when listening, usually meaning controlled speaking practice tasks. The feedback can be made even simpler to give and collect and more neutral with some careful planning, e.g. asking them count how many times their partner uses the target form as well as or instead of looking for when it used incorrectly.

14. Try again!

Sometimes, students don't need much help at all but just a chance to do it again. This is likely to be true if we have trained them well in spotting their

own errors, if there was some other kind of mental load such as a puzzle to solve that was distracting them from the language, or if they have had a chance to hear someone else doing the same speaking task in the class or on a recording.

15. Remind them when we studied that point

For example, “Nearly right, but you’ve forgotten the grammar that we studied last week” or “You’ve made the same mistake as everyone made in the last test”.

In testing a speaking skill, the criteria must be included in scoring the exercises. The criteria in scoring speaking base on the native criteria, like English language the criteria are taken by *The Common European Framework of Reference* (CEF) (Alderson et al, 2009:62). CEF (Council of Europe, 2001) is a problem for language education. It is used to help the students, teachers and other set goals for language learning and give them motivation to reach them. In the other hand, it includes a range of ‘illustrative descriptors’ of language performance, including any for speaking. The narrators have not been improved for some particular test, but they can use as a basis for innovating test-specific criteria. When its’ happen, it would be functioning to score some learner ability at different levels in the intended test situation to see if the descriptors correspond to them and if some more descriptions can be added, probably in the concrete style of the most detailed scale.

There are two types of scales in the CEF that have not yet been exemplified analyzing criteria that focus on linguistic features (Figure 2), and task-specific scales (Figure 3). Like most of the CEF scales, these have six levels: two at Basic (A1 and A2), two at Independent (B1 and B2), and two at Proficient (C1 and C2) (Alderson, 2009: 65).

The agreement if it has five criteria, the scale in figure2 is analytic, and given that it explains what the learners actually do, it is a charter rating scale. The explorer have been written for general rather than specific purposes, so that if it is used in a professionally specific speaking test, the functions and language-use contexts must be modified to suit that test. Beside the criteria focus on language, they create so from the general opinion of interactive communication. The connection scale provides some specific suggestions for wordings when rating interactive skills, while for assessing the tasks that require long turns by a speaker the coherence scale may provide any function concepts. If these criteria were used to compare performances on a speaking examination, the creators would have to make decision whether the examinees have to get five analytic scores, the combination of score as an overall score. They might also have to detail rules for creating the overall score. The decisions might depend on the heading for which they use in the test.

The scale in figure 3 is clearly delimited to a specific kind of talk. It only covers the lower end of the CEF scale because the expectation is that,

Table 2.1, Analytic descriptors of spoken language in Council of Europe, (2001: 28–29) (Aderson, 2009: 72)

	Range	Accuracy	Fluency	Interaction	Coherence
C 2	Shows good flexibility reformulating ideas for make differing linguistics forms to convey finer shades of meaning precisely, to give emphasis to differentiate and to eliminate ambiguity. Also has good statement of idiomatic expression and colloquialisms	Maintains include grammatical control of complex language, even while attention is otherwise engaged (e.g.in forward planning, in monitoring others' reactions)	Can make him/her spontaneously at length with a good natural colloquial flow, avoiding or backtracking around any difficulty so smoothly that the interlocutor is hardly aware of it.	Can improper with ease and skill, picking up and using non-verbal and into national cues apparently effortlessly. Can interweave his/her contribution into the point discourse with fully natural turn taking, referencing, allusion making, etc.	Can give coherent and cohesive discourse making full and appropriate use of a variety of organizational patterns and a wide range of connectors and other cohesive devices.
C 1	Has a good command of broad range of language allowing him/her to select a reformulation to express him/herself clearly in an appropriate style on a wide range of general, academic, professional or leisure topics without having to restrict what he/she wants to say.	Consistently maintains a high degree of grammatical accuracy; errors are rare, difficult to spot and generally corrected when they do occur.	Can express him/herself fluently and spontaneously, almost effortlessly. Only a conceptually difficult subject can hinder a natural, smooth flow of language.	Can select a suitable phrase from a readily available range of discourse functions to preface his remarks in order to get or to keep the floor and to relate his/her own contributions skillfully to those of other speakers.	Can produce clear, smoothly flowing, well structured speech, showing controlled use of organizational patterns, connectors and cohesive devices.
B 2	Has a sufficient range of language to be able to give clear descriptions and express viewpoints on	Shows a relatively high degree of grammatical control. Does not make errors which cause	Can produce stretches of language with fairly even tempo: although he/she can be	Can initiate discourse, take his/her turn when appropriate and end conversation	Can use a limited number of cohesive devices to link his/her utterances into

	most general topics, without much conspicuous searching for words, using some complex sentence forms to do so.	misunderstanding, and can correct most of his/ her mistakes.	hesitant as he/she searches for patterns and expressions. There are a few noticeably long pauses.	when he/she needs to, though he/she may not always do this elegantly. Can help the discussion along on familiar ground confirming comprehension, inviting others in, etc.	clear, coherent discourse, though there may be some 'jumpiness' in a long contribution.
B 1	Has enough language to fine by, with sufficient vocabulary to express him/her with some hesitation and circumlocutions on topics such as family, hobbies and interests, work, travel, and current events.	Uses reasonably accurately a repertoire of frequently used 'routines' and patterns associated with more predictable situations.	Can make comprehensibly, even though pausing for grammatical and lexical planning and repair is very evident, especially in longer stretches of free production.	Can initiate, maintain and close simple face to face conversations on topics that are familiar or of personal interest. Can repeat back part of what someone has said to confirm mutual understanding.	Can give link a series of shorter, discrete simple components into a connected, linear sequence of points.
A 2	Uses basic sentence patterns with memorized phrases, groups of a few words and formulae in order to communicate limited information in simple everyday situations.	Uses some simple structures correctly, but still systematically makes basic mistakes.	Can make him/her understood in very short utterances, even though pauses, false starts and reformulation are very evident.	Can answer questions and give respond to simple statements. Can analyst when he/she is following but is rarely able to understand enough to keep conversation going of his/her own accord.	Can link groups of words with simple connectors like 'and' and 'but' and 'because'.
A 1	Has a good basic statement of words and simple phrases related to personal details and	Shows only limited control of a few simple grammatical structures and sentence patterns in	Can make very short, isolated, mainly pre packaged utterances, with	Can answer and ask questions about personal details. Can interact in a	Can link words or groups of words with very basic linear connectors like

	particular concrete situations.	a memorized repertoire.	much pausing to search for expressions, to articulate less familiar words, and to repair communication.	simple way but communication is totally dependent on problem, rephrasing and repair.	'and' or 'then'.
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All the examples are included verbal definitions of the scale levels. This example is different in that there are several analytic scales, but the scale levels are only defined by numbers. The statement about speaking test for medical undergraduates at Melbourne University (Grove and Brown, 2001) is used to get the students who need support in their communication skills. From their first experience year of continue their study, the students must be studying communicate style with their patients in practicing sessions and collaborative working in small-group activities. The test was developed to provide detailed feedback to both native and nonnative speaker students to help them cope with the demands of their studies.

The result on the test is rated on two sets of criteria, one language- oriented and the other task-specific. The criteria in these examinations are depending to an informal discussion task on the topic of education. The examinees present and justify their opinions about it and discuss them with the examiner.

The scales in figure 3 are *numerical rating scales* (Aderson et al, 2009: 77), where the scales have titles, but the levels for every scale are only identified by numbers. This is useful when the raters can be hoped to agree about the meaning of the numbers. However, the interpretations of the scores usually vary across

raters because numbers in this sense are clear. When there is an even number of levels, according to this example, the raters need to make whether the examinee is on the weak or strong side of the middle point of information scale. The alternative is to have an odd number, but the difficulty with that solution is that the interpretation of the middle score may be particularly variable – very broad for some raters and rather narrow for others. This format of scales is therefore not very common in speaking assessment. More discussion rating information describes how students behave at each of the score levels, as in the earlier scale examples in this chapter. This gives a basis for greater rater agreement and more informative feedback. In the case of the Melbourne medical students' test, the raters have access to detailed descriptions of the meaning for information during the rating process. This includes examples of the kinds of communication behavior that the criteria mean (Grove and Brown, 2001). Unfortunately, these descriptions have not been shown. Nevertheless, this format is probably useful in situations like this, where new rating concepts are being explored. The information can be written out once the test has been used

Figure 2, *Task-specific numerical scales for an informal discussion task (Adapted from Grove and Brown, 2001)*

Adequacy of participation

Maintenance of interaction	6 5 4 3 2 1
Initiative, expansiveness	6 5 4 3 2 1

Quality of ideas

Maturity and quality of thought	6 5 4 3 2 1
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Interpersonal skills

Engagement, rapport	6 5 4 3 2 1
Nonverbal behavior	6 5 4 3 2 1
Coherence and expression	
Clarity of ideas	6 5 4 3 2 1
Cohesion and coherence	6 5 4 3 2 1
Register and tone	
Level of formality	6 5 4 3 2 1
Politeness	6 5 4 3 2 1
Directness	6 5 4 3 2 1
Tone of voice	6 5 4 3 2 1
Linguistic criteria	
Language	
Range of structure and vocabulary	6 5 4 3 2 1
Breadth and precision of expression	6 5 4 3 2 1
Accuracy	6 5 4 3 2 1
Production	
Pronunciation	6 5 4 3 2 1
Intonation, stress and rhythm	6 5 4 3 2 1
Voice quality	6 5 4 3 2 1

Base on the rating concepts that use in this example, the task-related criteria of ‘adequacy of participation’, ‘quality of ideas’ and ‘interpersonal skills’ are broader than usual for language tests. The tasks and criteria were developed together with the score users – medical educators at Melbourne University – and these were the kinds of concepts that they found important in the situations that the students meet outside the test. As this was what the scores were intended to be relevant to, the test developers defined the rating criteria accordingly.

D. Frame Work

This study was done to find out students' preferences for error feedback and giving explanation the correlation between them, suggesting more effective ways of treating students' spoken errors in English as Foreign Language settings. After explained the theories of error feedback and speaking skill, the frame work of the research is showed by the diagram below:

Figure 3. Frame work

E. Hypothesis

The research was an experimental by using experimental and control class. The research hypothesis was applying teacher error feedback, the students could improve their English speaking skill.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHOD

A. Research Design

This study was a quasi-experimental, applying, exploratory study. In this study, one treatment groups and one control group are used. The two treatment group received different types of feedback (code and encode), while the control group is received no speaking feedback on their conversation.

The present study explored the effects of error feedback the students speaking accuracy, fluency, and comprehensibility. This means, that the independent variable (feedback) manipulated (because all types of feedback are used) to examine any possible change in the speaking accuracy (dependent variable). Therefore, this study is a quasi-experimental study. The design of the research formulated as follows:

$$O_1 \quad X \quad O_2$$

 $O_1 \quad X \quad O_2$

O1 = Pre-test for group 1

O2 = Post-test for group 1

X = Treatment

O1 = Pre-test for group 2

O2 = post-test for group 2

(Gay, 2006)

The interrupted line is showed if the groups using non-randomly technique (Mursid, 2011:21).

In this experimental research, the researcher has used two groups taken as the investigation groups. Frankel and Wallen (1990; 52) said the design as comparison group design. One group is for the experimental group that receives teacher error feedback as a treatment, while another group is for control group that do not receive any treatment. The control group runs the teaching and learning process as they usually do in daily, using the lesson plan of the English Department. On the other words, one of the groups used conventional method by grouping way of teaching and learning process. Wijaya (2008) said that conventional method is a traditional way or called speech method, it is the oldest method which is used as an oral communication between teacher and students in teaching process While experimental group run teaching and learning process in which the classroom activities and lesson plan is implementing method activities which has prepared before. Fisher and Ellis (1990) emphasize that most of the definitions of a group indicate the sharing element among members as the key factor which defines the existence of a group. The sharing can be around perceptions, motivation or goals, as well as around tasks, such as in a scenario group session. This sharing element can be greatly influenced by the group dynamic or climate of the group. The structure of the group is another defining element - the roles, norms, values and power relationships that influence the behaviour of group members and tie them to the group, providing the 'glue' of

group structure. The structure of a group can influence the level and success of interaction in a group.

B. Research Variable and Operational Definitions

1. Research variable

The research consisted of one independent variable and two dependents variable. The independent variable of the research is teacher error feedback and the dependent variables are speaking skill and the students' responds and perceptions toward the error feedback given by teacher in speaking activities.

2. Operation definition

The operational variable was the specification of how the researcher defines and measures the variable. The variable termed that related to this research are as follow:

- a. The error refers to systematic learner's errors underlying knowledge of the language.
- b. Feedback is some response information concerning the comprehension and reception of the speaker's message given by the listener during a conversation.
- c. Speaking is probably the language skill that most language learners wish to perfect as soon as possible, it is the delivery of language through the

mouth and create sounds using many parts of our body, including the lungs, vocal tract, vocal chords, tongue, teeth and lips..

C. Population and Sample

1. Population

The population of the research was at English Department of Muhammadiyah University Makassar in academic 2012/2013. The researcher took the second semesters including seven classes namely 2A, 2B, 2C, 2D, 2E, 2F, and 2G every class consists of 35 students. Actually there were some grades semesters for this year like the second grade, the fourth grade, the six grades, and the eighth grade. The researcher had chosen the second grade semester because they as the beginner in speaking class. So the total of the students for the second semester at English Department of Muhammadiyah University Makassar was 245 students.

2. Sample

The sample of the research was the students at English Department of Muhammadiyah University Makassar in academic 2012/2013 especially for class 2F and Class 2A. There were two classes used in this research, the first was treatment class and the second was control class. The first class consisted of 33 students namely 2F and for treatment class and 2A for control class which consisted of 32 students. The researcher chosen both of them because they had similarity for the students performance after the researcher did

observation. The researcher had taken two of them as the sample of the research.

D. Research Instrument

The procedures in this study had the following order:

1. Pretest

The researcher used pre-test before treatment to identify the students' accuracy, fluency, and comprehensibility in speaking skill. The researcher observed the students naturally in pretest. The researcher had applied a pretest to the subject which aims at knowing and seeing how well the students' ability in speaking performance. In this stage the students discussed a topic with their own group. After that, every group made conclusion end than express in front of the class.

The pretest is a timing speaking test in which students asked to speak in-class speaking in two hours because every student need three until four minutes for speaking. The same test administered to both the control group and the two treatment groups. The control group took the pretest to control for the pretest effect. Therefore, the results were due to the treatment not the pretest.

2. Treatment

Pretest is a way to know the students' accuracy, fluency, and comprehensibility in speaking. After that, the researcher treated based on the

procedure feedback. In this stage, the research came to the class to teach the learner. The researcher made lesson plan based on the curriculum of Muhammadiyah University and focused in speaking class. The researcher has applied teacher error feedback in speaking. During the speaking class, the researcher analyzed the students' error in speaking. After analyzing their errors, the researcher gave some kind of feedback which base on the criteria in feedback types. The feedback types are a) Explicit correction, b) Recast, c) Classification requests, d) Metalinguistics feedback, e) Elicitation, and f) Repetition.

Teacher also applied conventional method by grouping in control class. The data took in control class would be analyzed like in experimental class. After analyzing the data, the researcher compared the result score between control class and experimental class and made conclusion.

3. Posttest

After the researcher gave the treatment, the researcher administrated a posttest to find out the value of the treatment whether or not speaking ability of the students improves. In this stage every students spoke base on the topic. After that, the researcher recorded their speaking to analyze and compare between pre-test and post-test.

4. Questionnaire

In getting accurate information about the students' response applying feedback, questionnaires is one of tool which used get it. According to

Taylor and John (2007:43) If the research project was going to involve the use of a questionnaire, then it's essential to put time and effort into getting the format right. The first step was to determine precisely what information the researcher needs to know, while thinking carefully about our hypothesis. Although it can be important to include relevant background questions, we need to make sure that the questions reflect the aims of our project and that we don't collect unnecessary data. Attempt to answer our own questions.

E. Procedure of Data Collection

1. Preparing the lesson plan

The lesson plan designed to implement during treatment to the experimental group. The researcher designs the lesson plan for four meetings. The first and the last meeting allocated to conduct pre-test and post-test, while the four meetings allocated to execute treatment (teacher error feedback). The lesson plan designed base on the curriculum at English Department of Unismuh Makassar. The lesson plan for the control group is made by the base on English department curriculum.

2. Preparing the material.

The material gave to the experimental and control group taking from several materials base on the English Department curriculum. The materials are:

- Opinion (pre-test)
- Asking and telling the time

- Apologizing
- Talking on the phone
- Asking about and giving opinion.
- Describing object
- Describe people physically
- Telling experience (post-test)

There are some material chosen in teaching, it is one way to minimize the students' boring in teaching. By combine the material, students still focused in teaching

3. Administering pre-test

Pre-test administered to both experimental and control group. The purpose of the test is gotten data about the students' basic speaking skill and to ascertain that the students from both groups have the same English proficiency before they receive the treatment. The procedure test is exactly same both of experimental and control groups.

4. Conducting treatment

The research designed to see the effect of two groups namely experimental and control group with different treatment. The experimental group designed to offer a special treatment by using kinds of feedback in teaching speaking on spoken produce text, while the control group with giving non treatment

only conventional including presentation, practice, and production.

According to Ahmadi (2005), conventional method is:

pendekatan konvensional ditandai dengan guru mengajar lebih banyak mengajarkan tentang konsep-konsep bukan kompetensi, tujuannya adalah siswa mengetahui sesuatu bukan mampu untuk melakukan sesuatu, dan pada saat proses pembelajaran siswa lebih banyak mendengarkan. Disini terlihat bahwa pendekatan konvensional yang dimaksud adalah proses pembelajaran yang lebih banyak didominasi gurunya sebagai “pentransfer ilmu, sementara siswa lebih pasif sebagai “penerima” ilmu.

In different statement, Wijaya (2008) said that conventional method is a traditional way or called speech method, it is the oldest method which used as an oral communication between teacher and students in teaching process.

Presentation involves the building of a situation requiring natural and logical use of the new language (Pollard, 2008: 25). When the "situation" is recognized and understood by the students, they will then start instinctively building a conceptual understanding of the meaning behind the new language, and why it will be relevant and useful to them. When the situation surrounding the new language and the conceptual meaning of it has been achieved, the new language should be introduced by means of a linguistic "model". It is this model that the students will go on to practice and hopefully achieve naturally without help during a productive activity.

For obvious reasons, it is naturally easier to "present" new language to ESL students (who are learning English as a Second Language in an English speaking environment) than it is to EFL (English as a Foreign Language)

students, who hear little or no English outside of the classroom. EFL teachers in particular need to work hard to build "realistic" feeling situations requiring the new language. If the "situation" appears totally unreal or even farcical to the students, so too will the language they are learning. An important aspect of introducing the situation requiring and concept underlying new language is to build them up using whatever English the students have already learned or have some access to. At lower levels, pictures and body language are typical ways of presenting new language. As students progress, dialogues and text can also be used. There are a variety of ways in which new language items may be presented but most Presentations should have at least some of the following features: meaningful, memorable and realistic examples; logical connection; context; clear models; sufficient meaningful repetition; "staging" and "fixing"; briefness and recycling.

The Practice stage is the best known to teachers irrespective of their training or teaching objectives (Pollard, 2008: 57). However, it is a stage that is often "over-done" or used ineffectively, either because Presentation was poor (or lacking altogether) or it is not seen and used as a natural step toward Production. It is the important middle stage to communicative language teaching, but exactly that the "middle" stage. It is important that practice activities are appropriate to the language being learned and the level and competence of the students. Essentially Practice is the testing procedure for accuracy, and the frequency procedure for familiarity with the language. It is

also a remedial stage. A good way to summarize effective Practice is to see it as repetition leading to competence and accuracy in terms of Phonology and Syntax.

Practice activities need to be clear and understandable - they should also be directed toward promoting a considerable degree of confidence in the students. In general, a carefully laid out practice activity that looks "attractive" to the eye will generate the students' motivation. They need to be challenged, but they should also feel that the activity is "within their reach". Making a smooth transition from Presentation to Practice usually involves moving the students from the Individual Drill stage into Pair Work (chain pair-work, closed pair-work and open pair-work). Communicative practice then leads the way toward Production.

The Production Stage is the most important stage of communicative language teaching. Successful Production is a clear indication that the language learners have made the transition from "students" of the key language to "users" of the language (Pollard, 2008: 59). Generally Production involves creating a situation requiring the language that was introduced in the Presentation Stage. That situation should result in the students "producing" more personalized language. Production is highly dependent on the Practice Stage, because if students do not have confidence in the language then they will naturally be hesitant to independently "use" it. One of the most important things to remember is that Production activities should not "tell" students what

to say. Whereas in Practice the students had most or all of the information required, during Production they don't have the information and must think. Ideally it is challenging in that it is representative of "real life" situations.

The treatment designed for four meetings. In contrast, the control group is treated using conventional method. the researcher used quasi experimental method, automatically used experimental and control class. Control class would be used conventional method and experimental would focus in giving feedback. The differentiation between control class and experimental class showed by the table below:

Table 3.1. The plan action between control class and experimental class

NO	Experimental Class	Control Class
1 st	Pre-Test	Pre-Test
2 nd	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Greeting and warming up - Making small groups which consist of 6-7 students and explaining material (telling experience). - Every group do discussion base on the material about. - Controlling the group and giving feedback - Recording the students speaking for analyzed in the next meeting - One of group member is chosen 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Greeting - warming up - Explaining material in front of class (telling experience) - Giving some examples before the students practicing. - Teacher chooses the students randomly for practicing the materials - Writing the students mispronunciation. - Retelling the students'

	<p>for speaking practice.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Metalingistic and explicit feedback after controlling all the groups. - Classification request (if anybody give question) - Conclusion and closing the meeting 	<p>mispronunciation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conclusion and closing the meeting
3 th , 4 th , 5 th , 6 th , and 7 th	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Greeting and warming up - Reviewing and evaluating the result of recorder. - Making 6 small groups which consist of 6-7 students and explaining material (apologizing). - Recording the students speaking for analyzed in the next meeting - One of group member is chosen for speaking practice. - Metalingistic and explicit feedback after controlling all the groups. - Classification request (if anybody give question) - Conclusion and closing the meeting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Greeting - warming up - Grouping - Explaining material in front of class (telling experience) - Giving some examples before the students practicing. - Teacher chooses the students randomly for practicing the materials - Writing the students mispronunciation. - Retelling the students' mispronunciation. - Conclusion and closing the meeting
8 th	Post testa	Post test

5. Administering post-test

The study employs the post test at the end of the research. It is used to measure the students' speaking skill after treatments. It is employed to both experimental and control groups. This is intended and also to find out the differences between students' score of both group. The post test is almost similar the pretest.

6. Admiring Questionnaire

Decide on the response format, a closed question provides a number of alternative answers from which a choice has to be made. An open-ended question allowed the respondent to formulate their own answer. There's no right or wrong approach. Our decision would be based on respondent motivation, method of administering the questionnaire, the topic covered, expertise and time spent developing a good set of unbiased responses. Each has advantages and disadvantages. We should be aware of the problems caused by questions that create an attitude, known as 'ratification', and we must also remember that what people tell us in answer to a question does not always reflect their actual behavior.

F. Techniques of Data Analysis

The researcher analyzed the data after connecting by using instrument. The process of data analysis did on the pre-test and post-test to find out the learners'

improvement in speaking by applying teacher error feedback. There were score and criteria which are settled to give brief explanation for every score given in assessing students speaking ability. The criteria of assessment in conducting pre-test and post-test were settled by the scoring base on Heaton criteria (1989). They are accuracy, fluency, and comprehensibility.

Table 3.2. The scoring test criteria for accuracy, fluency, and comprehensibility

No	Aspect	Score	Criteria
1	Accuracy	6 (excellent)	Pronunciation only very slightly influence by the mother tongue, two or three grammatical errors
		5 (Very good)	Pronunciation only very slightly influence by the mother tongue, a few minor grammatical and lexical errors but most utterance is correct
		4 (Good)	Pronunciation is still moderately influence by the mother tongue but no serious phonological errors. A few grammatical and lexical errors some of which cause confusing
		3 (Average)	Pronunciation seriously influenced by the mother tongue. Only a view serious phonological errors, and several grammatical and lexical errors some of which cause confusing
		2 (Poor)	Pronunciation seriously influenced by the mother tongue with errors causing a breakdown in communication many “basic” grammatical and lexical errors
		1 (Very poor)	Serious grammatical errors as well as many “basic” grammatical and lexical errors. No evidence of having mastered any of the language skills and areas practiced in the course.
2	Fluency	6 (excellent)	Speak without too great an effort with a fairly wide range of expression. Search for

			word occasionally by only one or two unnatural pauses
		5 (Very good)	Has to make an effort at time to search for words. Nevertheless, smooth, delivery on the whole and only a view unnatural pauses.
		4 (Good)	Although he has to make an effort and search for words, there aren't many unnatural pauses.
		3 (Average)	Has to make an effort for much of time. Often has to search for desired meaning. Frequently fragmentary and halting delivery. Almost give up making the effort at times. Limited time of expression.
		2 (Poor)	Long pause while he searches for desire meaning. Frequently fragmentary and halting delivery. Almost give up making the effort at time. Limited range of expression.
		1 (Very poor)	Full of long and unnatural pauses. Very halting and fragmentary delivery. At time gives up making the effort. Very limited range of expression.
3	Comprehensibility	6 (excellent)	Easy for the listener to understand the speaker, attention and general meaning. Very view interruption and classification required.
		5 (Very good)	The speaker intention and general meaning are fairly clear. View interruptions by listeners for sake of classifications are necessary.
		4 (Good)	Most of what the speaker says is easy to follow. His intention is always clear but several interruption are necessary to help him to convey message and to seek classification.
		3 (Average)	The listener can understand a lot of what is said, but he must consistently seek classification. Cannot understand many of the speaker' more complex or longer sentences.
		2 (Poor)	Only small bits (usually short sentences and phrases) can be understand and then with considerable effort by someone who is to

			listening to the speaker.
		1 (Very poor)	Hardly anything of what is said can be understood. Even when the listener make great effort or interruption. The speaker is unable to clarity anything they seems to have said.

In scoring the students' fluency, accuracy, and comprehensibility, their recorders made transcription. It used to make phonetic form based the students' ability in pre-test and post test. It was like the example below;

Accuracy	EXCELLENT	10	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She /fi:/, will /wil/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /in/, holiday /hɒlədeɪ/, with /wiθ/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /fæməli/</p>
		8,6	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She /fi:/, will /wil/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /in/, holiday /hɒlədeɪ /, with /wit/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /fæməli/</p>
	GOOD	8,5	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She /si:/, will /wil/, go /go/, to /tu/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /in/, holiday /hɒlɪdeɪ/, with /wit/, her /he(r)/, family /fæməli/</p>
		7,5	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p>

			She /si:/, will /wil/, go /gO/, to /tO/, the /də/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /in/, holiday /'hɒlɪdeɪ/, with /wit/, her /he(r)/, family /'fæmɪli/
	POOR	5,1	“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”. She /si:/, will /wil/, go /gO/, to /tO/, the /ðə/, beach /bɪtʃ/, in /in/, holiday /'hɒlɪdeɪ/, with /wit/, her /he(r)/, family /'fæmɪli/
	VERY POOR	4,0	“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”. She /si:/, will /wil/, go /gO/, to /tO/, the /de/, beach /bɪtʃ/, in /in/, holiday /'hɒlɪdeɪ/, with /wit/, her /he(r)/, family /'fæmɪli/
Fluency	EXCELLENT	10	“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”. She /fi:/, will /wil/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /in/, holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/, with /wiθ/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /'fæmɪli/
		8,6	“She will go to the beach with her family in holiday time”. She /fi:/, will /wil/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, with /wiθ/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /'fæmɪli/, in /in/, holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/, time /taɪm/
	GOOD	8,5	“She will go to the beach together with family”. She /si:/, will /wil/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /də/, beach /bi:tʃ/, together /tə'geðə(r)/, with /wiθ/, family /'fæmɪli/

	POOR	5,1	<p>“She will go to at beach together family in time holiday”.</p> <p>She /si:/, will /wil/, go /go/, to /tu:/, at /et/, beach /bi:tʃ/, together /tʊɡedə(r), family /'fæmili/, in /in/, time /taim/, holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/</p>
	VERY POOR	4,0	<p>“She will go to beach together family at time holiday”.</p> <p>She /si:/, will /wil/, go /go/, to /tu:/, beach /bɪtʃ/, together /tʊɡedə(r), family /'fæmili/, at /et/, time /taim/, holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/</p>
Comprehensibility	EXCELLENT	10	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She /ʃi:/, will /wil/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /in/, holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/, with /wiθ/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /'fæməli/</p>
	GOOD	8,6	<p>“She will go to the beach with her family in holiday time”.</p> <p>She /ʃi:/, will /wil/, go /go/, to /tu:/, the /də/, beach /bi:tʃ/, with /wiθ/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /'fæməli/, in /in/, holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/, time /taim/</p>
	POOR	5,1	<p>“She will goes to at beach with her family in holiday time”.</p> <p>She /ʃi:/, will /wil/, goes /gɒs/, to /tu:/, at /et/, beach /bɪtʃ/, with /wɪt/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /'fæməli/, in /in/, holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/, time /taim/</p>
	VERY POOR	4,0	<p>“She will to goes to at beach together family at time holiday”.</p>

			She /si:/, will /wil/, goes /gos/, to /tu:/, at /et/, beach /bich/, together /tugedə(r), family /'fæməli/, at /et/, time /time/, holiday /holidei/
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When the teacher had finished giving the score criteria, the next step is scoring the result of the students speaking. The way in scoring the result of the students' ability showed the table below:

Table 3.3. The scoring the result of the students' ability

Score	Classification
9,6 – 10,0	Excellent
8,6 – 9,5	Very good
7,6 – 8,5	Good
6,6 – 7,5	Fairly good
5,6 – 6,5	Fair
3,6 – 5,5	Poor
0 – 3,5	Very poor

(Depdikbud, 2004)

After scoring the students answer, the researcher would convert the students' score using the following formula:

$$\text{A Sudnt'sscore} = \frac{\text{The gain score}}{\text{The maxima; score}} \times 100$$

1. Data analysis on pre-test and post-test

The data obtained from the pre-test aimed to investigate the students' initial ability in speaking and is analyzed by the independent sample t-test statistics. There were three assumptions underline the t-test that the subject is allotted to one group in experiment, the variances' score are equal and normaly distributed, and the scores on independent variable are continuous. For that reason, test of normal distribution test and the homogeneity of variance test did before the t-test calculation by comparing the level of significance. For the data analysis, the score of the students both pre-test and post-test by using the formula:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{N}$$

Where:

\bar{X} = means score

$\sum X$ = The sum of all score

N = The total number of students

(Gay, 2006)

For finding the standard deviation of the students pre-test and post-test, the researcher applied the formula below:

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N - 1}}$$

Where:

SD = Standard deviation

$\sum X$ = Sum of all score

$(\sum X)^2$ = The square of $\sum X$

N = the total number of students

For finding the significant between pre-test and post-test in analyzing the data, we applied the formula:

$$t = \frac{D}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 - (\sum D)^2}{N(N-1)}}}$$

Where: $D = \frac{\sum D}{N}$

Where:

t = Test significant different

D = The different between the Matched Pairs ($X_2 - X_1$)

\bar{D} = The mean of D s (Difference score)

$\sum D^2$ = The sum of square

$(\sum D)^2$ = the square of $\sum D$

N = The total number of students

(Gay, 2006)

The independent sample of t-test also conducted in analyzing the post-test score in control and experimental group students to compare mean of both groups. After that, the calculation of effect size was going to conduct by using sample of t-test of post-test.

2. Data analysis on questionnaire

The questionnaires transcribed and classified to obtain information about teacher error feedback in implementing in the experimental group class. The administering questionnaire were aimed to find out the advantage and disadvantage of teacher error feedback implementation from the students' point of view and the students' strategies to overcome the obstacles in learning speaking by giving teacher error feedback.

CHAPTER IV

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

In this chapter is contained data finding from the test result. The data is included the result of pre test and post test. The data was analyzed by using the steps base on the procedure in chapter III. The chapter also presents the discussion in research finding.

A. Research Findings

The research finding was taken from the teaching process which consists of the description the result of the data analysis. The data analysis are the students speaking performance in teaching that skill in presenting the teacher error feedback. It was taken from the sample of the research which collected from 65 students at English Department of Muhammadiyah University Makassar in academic 2012/2013 especially for class 2F and Class 2A.

In collecting the data, the researcher was taken through pre-test that aims to know the students ability before giving treatment. Pre-test can give us information the students attitude before the research is started doing it. At the end of the meeting, the researcher gave the students post-test in order to know the effect teacher feedback in speaking ability after applying the treatment. The data also took from control class to compare with experimental class.

1. The descriptive of applying feedback

The research started on October 2013 and finished on December 2013. In applying teacher error feedback for experimental class, the researcher designed in to eight meeting. The first meeting was a pre-test, the second meetings until the seventh were activities in the classroom, and the eight was a post-test. In teaching, the activity was divided into three mains action like presentation, practicing, and production. The activities set base on the steps of our lesson plan for teacher error feedback.

The first material was about telling experience for example, there were some mistakes made the students while they are speaking as follow;

“I will tell my experience in spending night...there are some competition; I want to talking my experience in English department; my experience in English department... I get study and get many knowledge; I can coming join in English department.”

The researcher was using *explicit correction* to help the students correcting ungrammatical. It was always used because the students' stiles could be listened clearly. The researcher sometime used *recast* feedback to reformulate the students' utterance. In the other hand, the students also were produced mispronunciation like; abaut (about) for /ə'baʊt/; cheng (chance) for /tʃæns/; difikol (difficult) for /dɪfəkəlt/. The researcher applied *repetitions* for correcting the students' mispronunciation. In the last activities, the researcher sometime explained some general mistakes were made by students with *metalinguistic feedback*, it was a way to clarify the mistake and giving general information to the students.

The second material was about apologizing. In this activity, the students were divided into several groups and every group should practice. The researcher was given *explicit correction* and *recasts* when the students practicing how to apologize someone. It was applied like; I am sorry ... I am come late; pardon me because I have make you wait me; and some ungrammatical. The researcher was given also *repetitions* for some mispronunciation like; my vegetabel (vegetable) for /vejtbəl/; forgifme (forgive) for /fər'gif/, etc. There was no *recast* and *elicitation* in these activities, but in the last activities the researcher applied *metalinguistic feedback* to give comment and information about some ways to apologize politely.

The next materials in this research were describing object, people physically, and personality, include also about asking and giving opinion. These was same with the past materials, generally the students mistake were ungrammatical and mispronunciation. The most frequency of feedback was *explicit correction* and *repetition*, but sometime also used *recast*, *elicitation*, and *metalinguistics feedback*. It was seldom used *clarification request*.

Incorrect students' speaking was a classical problem for foreigner. It could correct with give positive feedback to them because it can motivate the students still getting spirit and loyalty studying English.

For control class, in every meeting the researcher was applied presenting, practicing, and producing. In presentation, the material was explained to the students based on the lesson plan. The material was same for experimental class but only the way to deliver the knowledge was different. The next activity after presentation was practicing the materials; it was applied for empowering the students' knowledge from the researcher. While the students' practicing the material, teacher was written their mistake. The last activities were producing and the students practice to produce base on the material. In the last activities, the researcher explained some notes from the past activities for giving correction to the students.

2. The result of descriptive data analysis

In scoring the speaking skill, the row score of the students is obtained through instrument and had been tabulated base on three criteria in assessing speaking namely accuracy, fluency, and comprehensibility. All the criteria and the percentage of the student score for experimental class in pre-test and post-test as follow:

a. Accuracy

1) Experimental class

The result of the data analysis from pre-test and post-test of the students in accuracy criteria for speaking is shown on the following table:

Table 4.1. The distribution of frequency and percentage score students' speaking in terms of accuracy in pre-test and pots-test.

Classification	Score	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	9,6 – 10	0	0	5	15.15
Very good	8,6 – 9,5	0	0	0	0
Good	7,6 – 8,5	0	0	15	45.45
Fairly good	6,6 – 7,5	6	18.18	11	33.33
Fair	5,6 – 6,5	0	0	0	0
Poor	3,6 – 5,5	14	42.42	2	6.06
Very poor	0 – 3,5	13	39.39	0	0
Total		33	100	33	100

Based on the table above after the research analyzing the data, pre-test shows there were 13 (39.39 %) of 33 students were included in very poor criteria. In poor level there were 14 (42.42 %) from 33 students as the sample, and there were 6 (18.18%) classified as fairly good. After the researcher got the students speaking test, we concluded that the students' speaking accuracy was poor in pre-test.

In the other hand, the table above also shows that no one of the students classified as very poor in accuracy. There were 2 (6.06 %) in poor level, 11 (33.33%) classified in fairly good, 15 (45.45%) students obtained good, and 5 (15.15%) were classified as excellent. The comparison between pre-test and post-test was showed that the students' accuracy in post-test is higher than pre-test.

The score and standard deviation also presented in the following table:

Table 4.2. The mean score and standard deviation of the students speaking ability in terms of the students' speaking in terms of accuracy in pre-test and pots-test

Test	Mean score	Standard deviation
Pre-test	4.45	1.53
Post-test	7.87	1.34
Different	3,42	0,19

The table above showed the means score of the students' accuracy in pre-test was 4.45 and 1.53 for the standard deviation. In post-test the means score of the students were 7.87 and 1.34 for standard aviation. The description between mean score and standard deviation of the students in post-test was higher than pre-test. It is same with the distribution of frequency and percentage students' ability in terms of accuracy.

2) Control Class

The result of the data analysis from pre-test and post-test of the students in accuracy criteria for speaking is shown on the following table:

Table 4.3. The distribution of frequency and percentage score students' speaking in terms of accuracy for control class in pre-test and pots-test.

Classification	Score	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	9,6 – 10	0	0	1	3.13
Very good	8,6 – 9,5	0	0	0	0
Good	7,6 – 8,5	0	0	4	12.5
Fairly good	6,6 – 7,5	0	0	17	53.13
Fair	5,6 – 6,5	0	0	0	0
Poor	3,6 – 5,5	7	21.86	10	31.25
Very poor	0 – 3,5	25	75.75	0	0
Total		32	0	32	0

Based on the table in control class, it showed that there were 25 (75.75%) students included in very poor class, and there were 7(21.86) students in poor class. After the researcher got the students speaking test, we concluded that the students' speaking accuracy was very poor in pre-test for control class.

In post-test, there were 10 (3125%) included poor class between 32 students, 17(53.13) students were included in fairly poor from 32 students, and only 1 (3.13%) student included in excellent criteria. The comparison

between pre-test and post-test was showed that the students' accuracy in post-test is higher than pre-test in control class.

The score and standard deviation also in control class presented in the following table:

Table 4.4. The mean score and standard deviation of the students speaking ability in terms of the student students' speaking in terms of accuracy in pre-test and pots-test

Test	Mean score	Standard deviation
Pre-test	3.38	1,08
Post-test	6,45	1.24
Different	3,07	0,16

The table above showed the means score of the students' accuracy in pre-test for control class was 3.38 and 1,08 for the standard deviation. In post-test the means score of the students were 6,45 and 1.24 for standard aviation. The description between mean score and standard deviation of the students in post-test was higher than pre-test. It is same with the distribution of frequency and percentage students' ability in terms of accuracy.

After calculating the students score both of experimental class and control class in pre-test and post-test, the means score and standard deviation both of experimental class and control class in pre-test and post-test were presented in the following table:

Table 4.5. The means score and standard deviation both of experimental class and control class in pre-test and post-test

Experimental	Pre-test	4.45	1.53
	Post-test	7.87	1.34
Different		3.42	0.19
Control	Pre-test	3.38	1,08
	Post-test	6,45	1.24
Different		3,07	0,16

b. Fluency

1) Experimental class

The result of the data analysis from pre-test and post-test of the students in fluency criteria for speaking is shown on the following table:

Table 4.6. The distribution of frequency and percentage score students' speaking in terms of fluency in pre-test and pots-test.

Classification	Score	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	9,6 – 10	0	0	6	18.18
Very good	8,6 – 9,5	0	0	0	0
Good	7,6 – 8,5	0	0	14	42.42
Fairly good	6,6 – 7,5	9	27.27	12	36.36
Fair	5,6 – 6,5	0	0	0	0
Poor	3,6 – 5,5	16	48.48	1	3.03
Very poor	0 – 3,5	8	24.24	0	0
Total		33	100	33	100

Based on the table above pre-test shows there were 8 (24.24%) of 33 students were included in very poor criteria. In poor level there were 16 (48.48 %) from 33 students as the sample, and there were 9 (27.27%) classified as fairly good. After the researcher got the students speaking test, we concluded that the students' speaking fluency was poor in pre-test.

In the other hand, the table above also shows that no one of the students classified as very poor in fluency. There was 1 (3.03 %) in poor level, 12 (36.36%) classified in fairly good, 14 (42.45%) students obtained good, and 6 (18.18%) were classified as excellent. The comparison between pre-test and post-test was showed that the students' fluency in post-test is higher than pre-test.

The score and standard deviation also presented in the following table

Table 4.7. The mean score and standard deviation of the students speaking ability in terms of the student students' speaking in terms of fluency in pre-test and pots-test

Test	Mean score	Standard deviation
Pre-test	5.03	1.32
Post-test	7.92	1.31
Different	2,89	0,01

The table above showed the means score of the students' fluency in pre-test was 5.03 and 1.32 for the standard deviation. In post-test the means score of the students were 7.92 and 1.31 for standard deviation. The description between mean score and standard deviation of the students in post-test was higher than pre-test. It is same with the distribution of frequency and percentage students' ability in terms of fluency.

2). Control Class

The result of the data analysis from pre-test and post-test of the students in fluency criteria for speaking in control class is shown on the following table:

Table 4.8. The distribution of frequency and percentage score students' speaking in terms of fluency for control class in pre-test and pots-test.

Classification	Score	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	9,6 – 10	0	0	0	0
Very good	8,6 – 9,5	0	0	0	0
Good	7,6 – 8,5	0	0	6	18.75
Fairly good	6,6 – 7,5	2	6.25	14	43.75
Fair	5,6 – 6,5	0	0	0	0
Poor	3,6 – 5,5	10	31.25	12	37.5
Very poor	0 – 3,5	20	62.5	0	0
Total		32	100	32	100

Based on the table above pre-test shows there were 20 (62.5%) of 32 students were included in very poor criteria. In poor level there were 10 (31.25 %) from 32 students as the sample, and there were 2 (6.25%) classified as fairly good. After the researcher got the students speaking test, we concluded that the students' speaking fluency was very poor in pre-test.

In the other hand, the table above also shows that no one of the students classified as very poor in fluency. There was 12 (37.5 %) in poor level, 12 (36.36%) classified in fairly good, 14 (43.75%) students obtained fairly good, and 6 (18.17%) were classified as good. The comparison between pre-test and post-test was showed that the students' fluency in post-test is higher than pre-test.

The score and standard deviation also presented in the following table

Table 4.9. The mean score and standard deviation of the students speaking ability in terms of the students' speaking in terms of fluency in pre-test and pots-test

Test	Mean score	Standard deviation
Pre-test	3.95	1.32
Post-test	6.30	1.31
Different	2,35	0,01

The table above showed the means score of the students' fluency in pre-test was 3.95 and 1.32 for the standard deviation. In post-test the means score of the students was 6.30 and 1.31 for standard deviation. The description between mean score and standard deviation of the students in post-test was higher than pre-test. It is same with the distribution of frequency and percentage students' ability in terms of fluency.

c. Comprehensibility

1) *The experimental class*

The result of the data analysis from pre-test and post-test of the students in comprehensibility criteria for speaking is shown on the following table:

Table 4.10. The distribution of frequency and percentage score students' speaking in terms of comprehensibility in pre-test and pots-test.

Classification	Score	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	9,6 – 10	0	0	4	12.12
Very good	8,6 – 9,5	0	0	0	0
Good	7,6 – 8,5	1	3.03	15	45.45
Fairly good	6,6 – 7,5	3	9.09	12	36.36
Fair	5,6 – 6,5	0	0	0	0
Poor	3,6 – 5,5	16	48.48	2	6.06
Very poor	0 – 3,5	13	39,39	0	0
Total		33	100	33	100

The table above shows that in pre-test there were 13 (39.39%) students got very poor, 16 (48.48%) classified in poor students, 3 (9.09%) and 1 (3.03%) classified good student. The conclusion of the data analysis showed that the comprehensibility of the students was poor.

The table above also showed in post-test that no one student classified as very poor in comprehensibility. There were 2 (6.06%) classified in poor level. There were 12 (36.36%) students obtained fairly good classification, and 4 (12.12%) classified in excellent. After we classified the data from post-test activity, we can take conclusion the post-test is higher than post-test.

The score and standard deviation also presented in the following table

Table 4.11. The mean score and standard deviation of the students speaking ability in terms of the student students' speaking in terms of comprehensibility in pre-test and pots-test

Test	Mean score	Standard deviation
Pre-test	4.45	1.53
Pre-test	7.87	1.34
Different	3,42	0,19

In table 4.6 is the means score and standard deviation. The table above showed that the means score of the students comprehensibly in pre-test was 4.45 mean score and 1.53 for standard deviation. The score in post-test showed 7.87 mean score and 1.34 for standard deviation. The

description between mean score and standard deviation of the students in post-test was higher than pre-test. It is same with the distribution of frequency and percentage students' ability in terms of compressibility.

2) *Control Class*

The result of the data analysis from pre-test and post-test of the students in comprehensibility criteria for speaking for control class is shown on the following table:

Table 4.12. The distribution of frequency and percentage score students' speaking in terms of comprehensibility in pre-test and pots-test.

Classification	Score	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	9,6 – 10	0	0	0	0
Very good	8,6 – 9,5	0	0	2	0
Good	7,6 – 8,5	0	0	10	31.25
Fairly good	6,6 – 7,5	2	6.25	13	40.63
Fair	5,6 – 6,5	0	0	0	0
Poor	3,6 – 5,5	13	40.63	2	6.25
Very poor	0 – 3,5	17	53.13	0	0
Total		32	100	32	100

The table above shows that in pre-test there was 17 (53.13%) students got very poor, 13 (40.63%) classified in poor students, 3 (9.09%)

and 2 (6.25%) classified fairly good student. The conclusion of the data analysis showed that the comprehensibility of the students was poor.

The table above also showed in post-test that no one student classified as very poor in comprehensibility. There was 2 (6.25%) classified in poor level. There was 13 (40.63%) students obtained fairly good classification, and 10 (31.25%) classified in good. There was no one classified in very good and excellent. After we classified the data from post-test activity, we can take conclusion the post-test is higher than post-test.

The score and standard deviation also presented in the following table

Table 4.13. The mean score and standard deviation of the students speaking ability in terms of the student students' speaking in terms of comprehensibility in pre-test and pots-test

Test	Mean score	Standard deviation
Pre-test	4.16	1.26
Pre-test	7.44	1.19
Different	3,28	0,07

In table 4.6 is the means score and standard deviation. The table above showed that the means score of the students comprehensibly in pre-test was 4.16 mean score and 1.26 for standard deviation. The score in post-test showed 7.44 mean score and 1.19 for standard deviation. The description between mean score and standard deviation of the students in

post-test was higher than pre-test. It is same with the distribution of frequency and percentage students' ability in terms of compressibility.

d. Speaking ability

1) *Experimental class*

The result of the data analysis from pre-test of the students ability which consist of 33 students as the sample of the research in measuring the effect of teacher feedback is shown on the following table:

Table 4.14. The distribution of frequency and percentage score students' speaking in pre-test and pots-test.

Classification	Score	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	9,6 – 10	0	0	0	0
Very good	8,6 – 9,5	0	0	9	27.27
Good	7,6 – 8,5	1	3.03	10	30.30
Fairly good	6,6 – 7,5	4	9.09	13	39.39
Fair	5,6 – 6,5	1	0	0	0
Poor	3,6 – 5,5	19	48.48	1	3.03
Very poor	0 – 3,5	9	39,39	0	0
Total		33	100	33	100

Based on the table above showed final score in experimental research for pre-test, there were 9 (39.39%) from 33 students classified as very poor, 19 (48.48%) students classified into poor score level. There were 4 (9.09%) classified fairly good, and only 1 (3.03%) classified as

very good score for speaking ability. The result of the data analysis concluded that the ability of the students was poor.

While in post-test, the table in final score showed that there was no one students classified in very poor score. Only 1 (3.03%) students were classified in poor score. There were 13 (39.39%) students classified into fairly good, 10 (30.30%) students classified in good class, and 9 (27.27%) students classified into very good class. The data was showed that the ability of the students was good after given treatment.

The score and standard deviation also presented in the following table below:

Table 4.15. The mean score and standard deviation of the students speaking ability in terms of the student students' speaking in terms of comprehensibility in pre-test and pots-test

Test	Mean score	Standard deviation
Pre-test	4.66	1.10
Post-test	7.84	1.08
Different	3,18	0,02

Base on the table 4.8, the mean score of the students speaking ability in pre-test was 4.66 and 1.10 for standard deviation. The post-test the means score 7.84 and 1.08 for standard deviation. It can be concluded that the mean score of the students speaking ability in post test is higher than pre-test, while the standard deviation in post-test is higher than a pre-test.

2) Control class

The result of the data analysis from pre-test of the students ability which consist of 32 students as the sample of the research in measuring the effect of teacher teaching is shown on the following table:

Table 4.16. The distribution of frequency and percentage score students' speaking in pre-test and pots-test for control class.

Classification	Score	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	9,6 – 10	0	0	0	0
Very good	8,6 – 9,5	0	0	0	0
Good	7,6 – 8,5	6	18.75	7	21.88
Fairly good	6,6 – 7,5	17	53.13	14	43.75
Fair	5,6 – 6,5	6	18.75	8	25
Poor	3,6 – 5,5	3	9.38	3	9.38
Very poor	0 – 3,5	0	0	0	0
Total		32	100	32	100

Based on the table above showed final score in control class research for pre-test, there were 3 (9.38%) from 32 students classified as poor, 6 (18.75%) students classified fair level. There was 17 (53.13%) classified fairly good, and 6 (18.75%) classified as good score for speaking ability. The result of the data analysis concluded that the ability of the students was fairly good.

While in post-test, the table in final score showed that there was no one students classified in very poor score. Only 3 (9.38%) students were classified in poor score. There were 8 (25%) students classified into fair, 14 (43.75%) students classified in fairly good class, and 7 (21.88%) students classified into good class. The data was showed that the ability of the students was fairly good after teaching process.

The score and standard deviation also presented in the following table below:

Table 4.17. The mean score and standard deviation of the students speaking ability in terms of the student students' speaking in terms of comprehensibility in pre-test and pots-test

Test	Mean score	Standard deviation
Pre-test	4.83	0.85
Post-test	6.75	0.76
Different	1,92	0,09

Based on the table 4.8, the mean score of the students speaking ability in pre-test were 4.83 and 0.85 for standard deviation. The post-test the means score 6.75 and 0.76 for standard deviation. It can be concluded that the mean score of the students speaking ability in post test is higher than pre-test, while the standard deviation in post-test is higher than a pre-test

3. The result of the inferential statistical analysis

a). Experimental class

Statistical analysis is used to answer the research hypothesis. In order to know the level of significance 0.05 for variables in pre-test and post-test with degrees of freedom (df)= N-1, where N is the number of students (experimental class is 33 students), and t-test for non independent was applied the following table:

Table 4.18: t-test value and t-table value of accuracy

Accuracy	t-test	t-table
	19.88	2.036

The table 4.17 shows that t-test value (32) for accuracy is higher than t-table value (2.036). In the other hand, for the level of significant (α)= 0.05 and degree of freedom (df)= 32 than t-test value =19.88 and t-table = 2.036. The value of t-test is greater than t-table (19.88>2.036). It means that the result of the students' value after the researcher was given error feedback that there was significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the students' accuracy of speaking.

Table 4.19: t-test value and t-table value of fluency

Fluency	t-test	t-table
	13.27	2.036

The table 4.18 shows that t-test value (32) for fluency is higher than t-table value (2.036). In the other hand, for the level of significant (α)= 0.05

and degree of freedom (df)= 32 than t-test value =13.27 and t-table = 2.036. The value of t-test is greater than t-table ($13.27 > 2.036$). It means that the result of the students' value after the researcher was given error feedback that there was significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the students' fluency of speaking.

Table 4.20: t-test value and t-table value of comprehensibility

Comprehensibility	t-test	t-table
	13.25	2.036

The table 4.18 shows that t-test value (32) for comprehensibility is higher than t-table value (2.036). In the other hand, for the level of significant (α)= 0.05 and degree of freedom (df)= 32 than t-test value =13.25 and t-table = 2.036. The value of t-test is greater than t-table ($13.25 > 2.036$). It means that the result of the students' value after the researcher was given error feedback that there was significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the students' comprehensibility of speaking.

Table 4.21: t-test of the students

Variable	t-test	t-table
X2-X1	4.86	2.036

Table 4.20 shows that for the level significance (α)= 0.05 and degree of freedom (df)= 32 than t-test value =4.86 and t-table = 2.036. In the other hand, for the level of significant (α)= 0.05 and degree of freedom (df)= 32 than t-test value =4.86 and t-table = 2.036. The value of t-test is greater than t-table (13.25>2.036). It means that there was significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the students speaking ability after given feedback in teaching process.

b) Control class

Statistical analysis is used to answer the research hypothesis. In order to know the level of significance 0.05 for variables in pre-test and post-test with degrees of freedom (df)= N-1, where N is the number of students (control class is 32 students), and t-test for non independent was applied the following table:

Table 4.22: t-test value and t-table value of accuracy

Accuracy	t-test	t-table
	3.65	2.039

The table 4.17 shows that t-test value (31) for accuracy is higher than t-table value (2.039). In the other hand, for the level of significant (α)= 0.05 and degree of freedom (df)= 31 than t-test value =3.65 and t-table = 2.039. The value of t-test is greater than t-table (3.65>2.039). It means that the result of the students' value after the researcher was taught that there

was difference between the pre-test and post-test of the students' accuracy of speaking.

Table 4.23: t-test value and t-table value of fluency

Fluency	t-test	t-table
	9.75	2.039

The table 4.22 shows that t-test value (31) for fluency is higher than t-table value (2.039). In the other hand, for the level of significant (α)= 0.05 and degree of freedom (df)= 31 than t-test value =9.75 and t-table = 2.039. The value of t-test is greater than t-table (9.75>2.039). It means that the result of the students' value after the researcher was taught that there was difference between the pre-test and post-test of the students' fluency of speaking.

Table 4.24: t-test value and t-table value of comprehensibility

Comprehensibility	t-test	t-table
	13.67	2.039

The table 4.17 shows that t-test value (31) for comprehensibility is higher than t-table value (2.039). In the other hand, for the level of significant (α)= 0.05 and degree of freedom (df)= 31 than t-test value =13.67 and t-table = 2.039. The value of t-test is greater than t-table (13.67>2.039). It means that the result of the students' value after the researcher was taught that there was difference between the pre-test and post-test of the students' comprehensibility of speaking.

Table 4.25: t-test of the students

Variable	t-test	t-table
X2-X1	29.6	2.036

Table 4.20 shows that for the level significance (α)= 0.05 and degree of freedom (df)= 31 than t-test value =29.6 and t-table = 2.036. In the other hand, for the level of significant (α)= 0.05 and degree of freedom (df)= 31 than t-test value =4.86 and t-table = 2.036. The value of t-test is greater than t-table (29.6>2.036). It means that there was significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the students speaking ability after given feedback in teaching process.

4. The students' response necessity of feedback

In getting the students' illustration the necessity of feedback, researcher was given some questionnaires. The questionnaires were made to know the students' response from the teachers' feedback. It was made by using liker's scale. There were 22 questions including all the activities which were shown when teacher is teaching in the classroom. The questionnaires were classified into some criteria like the frequency of feedback, the timing for treating students' error, the rate of each feedback, and the persons should treat the students' error.

There were 33 students given the questionnaire to know their response. The students' responses were shown the following table:

a. The essential of error feedback

Table 4.26 Students response of the essential teacher error feedback

Strongly agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly disagree	
11	33.33%	21	63.63%	0	0%	1	3.03%	0	0%

Table 4.17 is shown the response of the students in regarding the essential of error correction in teaching English. There were 11 or 33.33% students responded strongly agree the essential of error feedback, 21 or 63.63% agree, and only 1 or 3.03% disagree. It means that the students agree that they wanted their error to be corrected and gotten feedback by the teacher

Table 4.27. The students response for error feedback frequency

Always		Usually		sometimes		Occasionally		Never	
10	30.30%	19	57.57%	2	6.06%	2	6.06%	0	0%

Table 4.18 is shown that there were 10 students or 30.30% choosing “always” feedback frequency from their teacher, there were 19 students (57.57%) answered “usually” get feedback, 2 (6.06%) were chosen “sometime, and only 2 students (6.06%) were chosen “occasionally”. No one students was chosen “never”.

b. The timing the spoken error to be treated

Table 4.28. The result answer of the timing spoken error to be treated in giving feedback

The timing for treatment	Strongly agree/ Agree		Neutral		Disagree/ Strongly Disagree	
As soon as error are made	6	18,18	10	30,30	17	51,51
After finish speaking	30	90,90	0	0,00	3	0,90

After activities	16	48,48	8	24,24	9	27,27
The end of the class	7	21,21	11	33,33	15	45,45

Table 4.26 is illustrated the result of timing error to be treated for feedback from teacher. The agreement of the students got error feedback as soon as error are made, there were 6 (18.18%) students strongly agree, 10 (30.30%) students were neutral, and there were many students disagree or strongly disagree gotten feedback as soon as error made. If we compare between as soon as and after finish speaking, after finish speaking is more higher, we can see on the table there were 30 students or 90.90% strongly agree, no one was chosen neutral and only 3 students or 0.90% disagree. For the fifth question after the activities, there were 16 (48.48%) students strongly agree, 8 (24.24%) students were neutral, and 9 (27.27%) strongly disagree. In the other hand, there were 7 (21.21%) students strongly agree getting feedback in the end of the class, 11 (33.33%) students were choosing neutral, and there were 15 (45.45%) strongly disagree getting feedback in the end of the class.

c. The students response on the types of error which need is treated

Table 4.29. Students response on type of error which need treating in teaching English

Error types	Always		Usually		Sometime		Occasionally		Never	
Serious	1	3,03	4	12,12	23	69,69	2	6,06	3	9,09
Less serious	1	3,03	23	69,69	3	0,90	6	18,18	0	0,00
Frequent	1	3,03	2	6,06	25	75,75	5	15,15	0	0,00
Infrequent	0	0,00	3	9,09	22	66,66	7	21,21	1	3,03
Individual	0	0,00	0	0,00	24	72,72	8	24,24	1	3,03

Table 4.27 shows that in the students highest anxiety group was 23 (69.69%) wanted serious error to be sometime treated, and 4 (12.12%) students were serious error to be usually treated, 5 (15.15%) students wanted to be occasionally, only 1 (3.03%) student was wanted to be always treated, but there were 3 (9.09%) students to be never treated. It closed with serious error, less serious and frequent were in the highest group, the less serious there were 23 (69.60%) students wanted to be usually treated and 3 (0.90%) wanted to be sometime treated, 6 (18.18%) students wanted to be occasionally treated, only 1 (3.03%) wanted to be always treated and also no one wanted to be never treated. In frequent group also wanted similar, 1 (3.03%) student to be always treated, 3 (3.03%) students wanted to be usually treated, 22 (66.66%) students wanted to be sometime treated, 7 (21.21%) students wanted to be occasionally treated, and only 1 (3.03%) wanted to be never treated.

d. The rate of each feedback

Table 4.30. The rate of feedback from the teacher in speaking

Feedback types	Very effective/ effective		Neutral		Ineffective/ very ineffective	
Implicit correction	11	33.33%	14	42.42%	8	24.24%
Explicit correction	30	90.90%	3	9.09	0	0.0%
Recasts	18	54.54%	10	30.30%	5	15.15%
Clarification requests	18	54.54%	6	18.18%	9	27.27%
Metalinguistic feedback	16	48.48%	8	24.24%	9	27.27%
Elicitation	21	63.63%	12	36.36%	0	0.0%
No corrective feedback	6	18.18%	10	30.30%	17	51.51%
Repetition	20	60.60%	6	18.18%	7	21.21%

Table 4.28 shows that almost kinds of feedback were given responses similar. In implicit correction, the students response were 11 (33.33%) chosen very effective, 14 (42.42%) were neutral, and only 8 (24.24%) were chosen very ineffective. The most popular type of feedback is explicit correction where there were 30 (90.90%) students chosen as an very effective feedback, only 3 (9.09%) were neutral and no one answered very ineffective. Different of recasts, there were 18 (54.54%) students responded ferry effective, 10 (30.30%) were chosen neutral, and 5 (15.15%) were chosen as very ineffective. In classification requests, there were 18 (54.54%) students answered very effective, 6 (18.18%) students were neutral, and 9 (27.27%) students were very effective. For metalinguistic feedback, there were 16 (48.48%) students agree if it was very effective, 8 (24.24%) students were neutral, and 9 (27.27%) students were answered very ineffective. Elicitation is

gotten higher response after explicit correction, 21 (63.63%) students were answered that elicitation very effective, only 12 (36.35%) were chosen neutral and no one students were chosen very ineffective. The next item about no corrective feedback, only 6 (18.18%) students answered very effective, 10 (30.30%) students were chosen neutral, and 17 (51.51%) students were answered very ineffective if no corrective feedback. The last item is repetition, there were 20 (60.60%) students chosen if repetition very effective, 6(18.18%) students were neutral, but 7 (21.21%) students were answered very ineffective. After we rate kinds of feedback, we can take conclusion if generally all kinds of feedback is needed depend on the skill the teacher is learned in learning activity.

e. the persons should treat the students error

Table 4. 30 The students respond should treat their error

Agents	Strongly agree/ Agree		Neutral		Disagree/ Strongly Disagree	
Classmates	17	51.51%	13	39.39%	3	9.09%
Teachers	21	63.63%	5	15.15%	7	21.21%
Students	20	60.60%	10	30.30%	3	9.09%

Table 4.29 shows the students respond who should treat their error in speaking English. There were 17 students (51.51%) strongly agree with their classmates, 13 (39.39%) were chosen neutral, but there were 3 (9.09%)

students strongly disagree if their classmates treat their error. In the other section, there were 21 (63.63%) students strongly agree if their teacher gave them treat in their error, there were 5 (15.15%) students neutral and only 7 (21.21%) were strongly disagree. Besides that, students also were given response if their friends should treat their error, in this case there were 20 (60.60%) students strongly agree another students gave them treat, 10 (30.30%) students were chosen neutral, and only 3 (9.09%) were chosen strongly disagree.

B. Discussion

1. The effectiveness of teacher error feedback

The discussion deals with description of the research. The description includes experimental class and control class where for experimental class applying teacher error feedback and for control class only conventional approach.

a. The students speaking accuracy

The descriptive analysis describes the students accuracy in speaking was improved from poor to good category, it was supported by showing it table 4.2 about the mean score and standard deviation of the students speaking ability of the students' speaking in terms of accuracy in pre-test and pots-test for experimental class. The mean score of pre-test 4.45 with standard deviation1,53 and mean score of post-test 7.87 with standard deviation 1.34. The different between pre-test and post test was 3.42. In accuracy, there were 13 students before treatment from 20

students classified as very poor but after giving treatment none of the students classified into very poor. Base on the result of the students speaking ability, the problem that faced by the students in implementing of teacher error feedback was the accuracy which relates with pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary. According to Liu (2008) error feedback in speaking classes needs a careful treatment because every learner will give different reactions to the feedback given by teachers. The students' accuracy in speaking after the treatment was given solution for them to minimize their mistake.

In improving the students' accuracy, it wasn't an easy job because our mother tongue still was given accuracy in our pronunciation. The students' mispronunciation for example was a problem for our students. In speaking, they said; difikol (difficult) for /difəkəlt/. To minimize that problem, *repetition* as a kind of feedback could use correcting the students' utterance. For empowering the students' fluency in speaking, *metalinguistic feedback* and *elicitation* feedback applied in teaching process. It was supported by Lyster and Ranta (2001) if some kinds of feedback should give positive impact clarified the students' error in teaching a language. Not only pronunciation but also ungrammatical form utterance produced the students' while speaking. It problem could be minimized by applying explicit *correction*, it could help students producing statements in speaking. Teacher can indicate that the students said incorrect form and the students got directly correction from their teacher.

The most important component that influences the students is their mother tongue as the first language, It was influenced the students in speaking (Russell, 2006). Teacher as the subject with good oral error feedback strategies can boost student motivation, advance language learning, and increase student perception of instructional effectiveness in the classroom whatever they teach English as foreign language.

In different case for control class, even the students was improved their speaking accuracy from poor to good category but the experimental class is higher than control class. It was showed in table 4.4. The means score of pre-test 3.38 with standard deviation 1.08 and mean score for post-test 6.45 with standard deviation 1.24. In accuracy for control class, there were 25 students before teaching from 32 students classified as very poor, but after teaching process none of the students classified into very poor.

The differentiation scores of the students between experimental class and control class was made fact that teaching English as foreign language needed approach which can make the students giving reaction whatever in EFL context. The main purpose of speaking class is to make students can use the language they have learned (Maria; 2010). Giving error feedback in teaching a language is one of approach ignoring the students' errors, it is highlighted that everyone is learning, and making errors is one of the signals that learning takes place; hence, each student is strongly encouraged not to laugh at others' mistakes. Both the teachers and students need to be aware of the importance of constructive corrections.

b. The students speaking fluency

Fluency is meaning speak without too great an effort with a fairly wide range of expression, search for word occasionally by only one or two unnatural pauses. In this research, it was used teacher error feedback to minimize the students' ungrammatical utterance in speaking especially *explicit correction*. It applied like; I will tell... my experience in..in.. spending night...there are some competition. Teacher could say; just tell or do you means“ in spending night, there were some competition”, that way helped student to produce simple and effective sentence when they practiced in the classroom. In the last activities, teacher also gave *metalinguistic feedback* to clarify all the notes in the past activity for that meeting and empowering students.

The students speaking fluency has similarity because the comparison control class and experimental class were showed that both improving the students speaking fluency, where experimental class is higher than control class.

In table 4.6 showed that the students fluency in speaking were improved from poor to good category. The fluency dealing with being fluent or no time for searching words in a time (Al Qahtani: 2011). It was supported with showing the mean score of pre-test 5.03 with standard deviation 1.32 and post-test 7.92 with standard deviation 1.31. In pre-test, the data analysis showed that none of the students classified excellent and very good score. But in post-test none of the students classified very poor but 1 (3.03%) of the student classified poor, there

were 26 (78.78%) students in good category and 6 (18.18%) students classified excellent.

The result of data analysis we concluded that there were significant improvement of students fluency in speaking. This is indicated that students should be practicing and getting control when speaking. Applying teacher error feedback in the speaking class was made students getting consideration to minimize their error, it is also supported by Paul (2011) statement that with suitable error feedback strategy can boost students' motivation, advance language learning and raise students perception of the effectiveness instructional because oral error feedback strategy build confidence and create a satisfying learning experience.

In the other hand, even using conventional way teaching English there were improved, it showed in table 4.8 where the mean score of pre-test 3.95 with standard deviation 1.32 and the mean score of post-test 6.30 with standard deviation 1.31. In pre-test for control class, the data analysis showed that none of the students classified excellent and very good score but there were 30 students classified poor. In post-test the students fluency was improved even none of the students got excellent.

The effectiveness applied teacher error feedback in experimental class. It was vital element in their teaching. Its purpose is to justify to students how their mark or grade was derived, as well as to identify and reward specific qualities in their work, to recommend aspects needing improvement, and to guide students on what steps to take. According to Ali (2005) feedback has function to define

students what their teacher thinks is important for a topic or a subject to manage their error in practicing soft skill in English. The statement was supported this research that how teacher feedback had changed the students ability better than before the treatment.

It was closed Lyster and Ranta (2001) statement that the decision to identify the error, there were two important attributes to an error feedback interaction. One is the identity of the error which made in teaching by students, it may be specifically pinpointed or left for the students to determine on their own. A second attribute is whether or not the feedback interaction explicitly identifies the fact that an error was made.

c. The students speaking comprehensibility

Easy for the listener to understand the speaker, attention and general meaning and Very view interruption and classification required is meaning the students having comprehensibility. In improving the students' speaking skill, feedback was given result to be better because the students more confidence and easier to understand each other. In teaching process, researcher was used *classification request* if any misunderstanding while speaking. The comprehensibility also could minimize by *metalinguistic feedback* because teacher asked them to analyze their error.

The students' speaking compensability is leading to the ability to be understood or intelligible. The result of data analysis in experimental class for the students comprehensibility in speaking was shown that teacher error

feedback was given effect. It was supported showing the mean score of pre-test 4.45 with standard deviation 1.53 and the mean score of post-test is 7.84 and 1.08 for standard deviation. The data shown that from the result of the students speaking, almost of the students speaking can be understood although they still did many mistake in term of grammar, pronunciation, and the use of vocabulary. Base on the data in pre-test, none of the students classified excellent and very good; some of them made mispronunciation an ungrammatical in speaking. After the students controlled in teaching by applying teacher error feedback, in post-test shown that there were improvement, none of the students in very poor category, only 2 (6.6%) students in poor category, 12 (36.36%) fairly good, 15 (45.45%) very good category, and 4 (12.12%) students excellent category.

Teacher error feedback was given good effect in helping students improving their skill in speaking English. It approach shown positive result where the students could get feedback from the teacher. It is supported by Al Asaeed (2010) that the main benefit attributes of teacher error feedback is that it highlights choices to teachers that allow them to customize feedback for the specific needs of the learner. For students who demonstrate a great degree of anxiety and discomfort about oral error feedback, for instance, teachers might provide recasts or prompts with little or no identification of the error. While for students who possess confidence, teachers might more boldly identify the fact an error was committed and, possibly, the specific nature of the error.

In analyzing data of control class, there were different score gotten even still any improvement but Experimental score is higher than control class. In control class, the data analysis was supported by showing the mean score of pre-test 4.16 with standard deviation 1.26 and the main score of post-test 7.44 with standard deviation 1.19. It supported that error teacher feedback better than conventional method.

This research was supported another researcher before like the research did by Pan (2010) who investigated the teacher feedback on the accuracy of EFL student writing. He made conclusion in his research if teacher feedback had advanced the students in better linguistic knowledge and it develop improved accuracy the students writing with higher degree than beginner after receiving teacher error feedback. It was same done by Ali (2005:49) that the effect of different types of feedback on second language writing over the course of a year but found no significant difference on learner's essays with regard to linguistic accuracy.

2. The students responds of teacher error feedback

There were 22 items of question given to the students to know their response about teacher error feedback, The items consisted of five general items including the essential of the feedback, timing the spoken error to be treated, the students response on the types of error which need is treated, rating of each feedback, and the persons should treat the students error.

The first general item is about the essential of teacher error feedback which includes two questions. The first question was about the students response of the essential teacher error feedback, students as the respondents generally answered agree. There were 33 students or 96.96% agree if teacher error feedback very essential and only 1 student or 3.03% was disagreeing. This is indicated that students think their spoken error should be corrected when teaching language whatever English as foreign language. It is supported by Ancker (2000) studied that the students wanted their spoken errors to be treated more than the teacher the teacher thought.

The next question was about the frequency of teacher error feedback. There were 10 or 30.30% students wanted *always* corrected from teacher, 19 students or 57.57% answered *usually* frequency corrected, 2 or 6.06% were chosen *sometime* frequency corrected and only 2 or 6.06% students were chosen *occasionally* corrected, but none of students thought that their errors should *never* be corrected by teacher. The finding of the research indicated that students usually to correct their errors more frequency (Ancker, 2000).

The second general item is the essential of error feedback which consist of four statements. The first statement indicated that there were 6 or 18.18% students agree to be treated as soon as errors are made by them, 10 or 30.30% students were neutral, and there were more than half of classmate or 51.51% disagree as soon as errors are made. It suggested that interrupting the students speaking in order to treat error was not a good option for teacher (Park, 2010:

32) because who were focused on accuracy in their teaching English but sometime teacher regarded fluency and comprehensibility as well as accuracy as one of crucial factor to the students as the development of speaking skills. The second statement about the timing the spoken error to be treated had different responded from students, there were 30 students or 90.90% strongly agree after finishing speaking, none of the students were chosen neutral and only 3 students or 0.90% disagree after finishing speaking. It was indicated that after finishing speaking to be the most appropriate time to treat errors in teaching. The third statement was close with the second statement after the activities, there were 16 (48.48%) students strongly agree, 8 (24.24%) students were neutral, and 9 (27.27%) strongly disagree. The students believed that correcting spoken errors after completing the communicative activities can enhance both accuracy and fluency since this allows the students to engage in communication without interruption caused by error treatment. The fourth statement was about the spoken error to be treated at the end of the class. The data analysis showed that there were 7 (21.21%) students strongly agree getting feedback in the end of the class, 11 (33.33%) students were choosing neutral, and there were 15 (45.45%) strongly disagree getting feedback in the end of the class. It was indicated that the students had no statistically significant different opinions about when to treat spoken errors.

The third general item was about the students' response on the types of error which need is treated which consist of five statements. The first statement

was serious spoken error where only 1 (3.03%) student was wanted to be always treated, 4 (12.12%) students were serious error to be usually treated, 23 (69.69%) wanted serious error to be sometime treated, 5 (15.15%) students wanted to be occasionally, but there were 3 (9.09%) students to be never treated. Overall, this was indicated that the students wanted error correction regardless should be treated whatever the types of errors did by them. The second statement was about less serious spoken error. It closed with serious error, less serious and frequent were in the highest group, the less serious there were 23 (69.60%) students wanted to be usually treated and 3 (0.90%) wanted to be sometime treated, 6 (18.18%) students wanted to be occasionally treated, only 1 (3.03%) wanted to be always treated and also none wanted to be never treated. The third was frequent of spoken error. In frequent group also wanted similar, 1 (3.03%) student to be always treated, 3 (3.03%) students wanted to be usually treated, 22 (66.66%) students wanted to be sometime treated, 7 (21.21%) students wanted to be occasionally treated, and only 1 (3.03%) wanted to be never treated. The second and the third statement had similarities percentage; it was a fact that generally student wanted corrective feedback usually on their frequent error because none of the students wanted never correcting them. The fourth was the individual of spoken error. The data shown that none of the students wanted always and usually treating, 24 (72.72%) wanted sometime treating, 8 or 24.24% wanted occasionally, and only 1 or 3.03% wanted never with individual. It is indicated that the students wanted

their teacher focus more on their serious spoken errors than individual errors. It is not realistic to expect that teachers provide their students with corrective feedback on individual errors in a classroom setting because it could influence their confidence (Park, 2010; 36). These findings indicated if teacher focus more on serious and frequent errors made by their students rather than correcting infrequent and less serious errors in speaking class. By focusing on serious and frequent spoken errors, teachers could help students in enhance the students' accuracy, fluency and comprehensibility.

The fourth general item was about the rate of each feedback. There were eight kinds of feedback presented in teaching the students; they were implicit correction, explicit correction, recast, classification request, metalingusitic feedback, elicitation, no corrective feedback and repetition. The students were asked to rate each item on five points scale; very effective, effective, neutral, ineffective, and very ineffective. The first item was about implicit correction. In implicit correction, the students response were 11 (33.33%) student chosen as an effective method, there were 14 or 42.42% students neutral, and only 8 (24.24%) were chosen very ineffective. Different with implicit correction, explicit correction as the second item was the most popular feedback in teaching speaking. There were 30 (90.90%) students chosen as a very effective feedback, only 3 (9.09%) were neutral and none of students answered very ineffective. Explicit correction refers to the explicit provision of the correct form, as the teacher provides the correct form, he or she clearly indicates that what the

student said is incorrect and teacher can make correction (Lyster & Ranta, 2001:67). It was the most popular type of corrective feedback used in speaking. The students highly valued explicit feedback over implicit feedback since direct feedback that points out the location of the error can increase the chance of modification and accelerate teaching. The students also favored elicitation that can help students produce the target language.

The third was recast; it means teacher's reformulation of all or part of a student's utterance, minus the error in teaching language skills. There were 18 (54.54%) students regarded effective feedback, 10 (30.30%) were chosen neutral, and 5 (15.15%) were chosen as very ineffective. It is a surprising result since many previous studies have shown that recasts are the most frequently used corrective feedback by teachers in the second language classroom although they are not the most effective method to correct learners' spoken errors due to ambiguity and implicitness (e.g., Ellis & Sheen, 2006; Lyster, 2004; Yoshida, 2008).

The fourth item was classification request. In classification requests, there were 18 (54.54%) students answered very effective, 6 (18.18%) students were neutral, and 9 (27.27%) students were very effective. The result indicated a discrepancy between teachers' beliefs and their actual practices. Besides that, teacher didn't use the type of feedback they were considered most of effective in actual teaching. Considering the fact that the researcher was based on the students respond, it may not be aware of teacher actual practices. These

responses were based on their ideal types of corrective feedback. In this research, students in both the high and low anxiety groups regarded recasts as an effective corrective feedback type (Pang, 2010).

The fifth item was metalinguistic feedback. For metalinguistic feedback, there were 16 (48.48%) students agree if it was very effective, 8 (24.24%) students were neutral, and 9 (27.27%) students were answered very ineffective. Metalinguistic feedback was not the popular type of feedback. This finding suggests that the learners think grammatical explanations do not help them modify their original utterances, or produce target-like forms, they still felt that another type of teacher feedback was more effective than others in improving their speaking skill.

The sixth was elicitation. Elicitation was gotten higher response after explicit correction, 21 (63.63%) students were answered that elicitation very effective, only 12 (36.35%) were chosen neutral and no one students were chosen very ineffective. It was the second favored type of corrective feedback frequency choosing.

The seventh was no corrective feedback. Only 6 (18.18%) students answered very effective, 10 (30.30%) students were chosen neutral, and 17 (51.51%) students were answered very ineffective. It was ineffective although the feedback type was the least popular among the students regardless of their anxiety levels. The researcher took conclusion that the students may value the time they can practice their speaking in class without correction. Given the fact

that some students can notice their spoken errors right after they make mistakes, no corrective feedback is sometimes useful using by teacher.

The eighth was repetition. There were 20 (60.60%) students chosen if repetition very effective, 6(18.18%) students were neutral, but 7 (21.21%) students were answered very ineffective. It was one of favored types of corrective feedback. Pan (2010) also suggested that repetition had given different result to the students accuracy and fluency in speaking. Repetition was informed that an error had been made and thus can lead them to produce the target language by modifying the formed utterance or pronunciation.

The fifth general item was about the persons should treat the students error. There were three types delivering agent of error correction; classmate, teacher, and students. The first statement indicated if there were 17 students (51.51%) strongly agree with their classmates, 13 (39.39%) were chosen neutral, but there were 3 (9.09%) students strongly disagree if their classmates treat their error. It was the lowest chosen by students. Choosing teacher should treat their error is the most highest of the students agree that they should correct by their teacher. The data showed there were 21 (63.63%) students strongly agree if their teacher gave them treat in their error, there were 5 (15.15%) students neutral and only 7 (21.21%) were strongly disagree. The second statement closed with the last statement, in this case there were 20 (60.60%) students strongly agree another students gave them treat, 10 (30.30%) students were chosen neutral, and only 3 (9.09%) were chosen strongly disagree. This

result of the research shown that more anxious students are more open to the corrective feedback from various agents, such as teachers, peers, and themselves, than less anxious students (Park, 2010). This indicates that more anxious students are more concerned in accuracy than less anxious students. Thus, their anxiety level increases when they speak English for speaking skill.

CHAPTER V

CONCLUSION

A. Conclusion

There are three criteria in assessing speaking namely accuracy, fluency, and comprehensibility. All the criteria was measured from the students to know the effectiveness teacher error feedback.

1. The students speaking accuracy in experimental class is higher than control class even both improving the students' ability. The data analysis in experimental class showed the students' speaking in terms of accuracy in pre-test and pots-test for experimental class. The mean score of pre-test 4.45 and mean score of post-test 7.87. In control class showed means score of pre-test 3.38 and mean score for post-test 6.45. It is indicated that effect of teacher error feedback more effective than conventional method.
2. The students speaking fluency also was improved after the treatment because experimental class is higher than control class. The mean score of pre-test is 5.03 and the mean score of post-test is 7.92. The result of data analysis concluded that there was significant improvement of students' fluency in speaking.
3. The result of data analysis in experimental class for the students comprehensibility in speaking was shown that teacher error feedback was given effect, the mean score of pre-test is 4.45 and the mean score of post test

is 7.85. It is indicated that Teacher error feedback was given good effect in helping students improving their skill in speaking English.

4. The students respond about the essential of error feedback shown that There were 11 or 33.33% students responded strongly agree the essential of error feedback, 21 or 63.63% agree, and only 1 or 3.03% disagree. It means that the students agree that they wanted their error to be corrected and gotten feedback by the teacher. The students response for error feedback frequency that there were 10 students or 30.30% choosing “always” feedback frequency from their teacher, there were 19 students (57.57%) answered “usually” get feedback, 2 (6.06%) were chosen “sometime, and only 2 students (6.06%) were chosen “occasionally”. None of the students was chosen *never*.
5. The students responds shout treat their error generally strongly agree if their teacher gives them treat their error in speaking. They also agree if their friends should treat their error.
6. The most popular corrective feedback in teaching speaking is explicit correction, elicitation, and repetition. They have effective function in detecting the students mispronunciation and low accuracy and fluency . The other corrective feedback like implicit correction, recast, clarification request, and metalinguistic feedback are not favored because the percentage is lower than other corrective feedback. It is indicated that not all corrective feedback effective use in speaking, depend on the skill.

B. Suggestion

1. Teachers should use consistent and standardized methods to indicate to their students the type and place of errors. They should know their students level before continuing their lesson, Lower level learners particularly will have trouble with finding the appropriate word and they need more modeling. Provide correct vocabulary choices
2. Teacher has to stress different things at different times. When the learners are making so many mistakes, it may be futile for the teacher to try to correct every error on the student speaking. Conferencing is a particularly useful technique to show the learners the errors in their speaking. Students can directly ask the teacher questions on the issues they have trouble with. At the same time the teacher may check the students' meaning and understanding.
3. This research will be complete if another searcher can continue to investigate all aspects of corrective feedback because the result of the research can apply minimizing the weakness in teaching.

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Appendix A

Experimental Class

The classification of the students' Accuracy in pre test and post test

No.	Sample	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Score	Classification	Score	Classification
1.		4	Good	5	Very Good
2.		3	Average	5	Very Good
3.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
4.		2	Poor	4	Good
5.		1	Very Poor	3	Average
6.		3	Average	5	Very Good
7.		3	Average	4	Good
8.		2	Poor	4	Good
9.		3	Average	5	Very Good
10.		3	Average	6	Excellent
11.		4	Good	6	Excellent
12.		4	Good	6	Excellent
13.		3	Average	5	Very Good
14.		3	Average	4	Good
15.		2	Poor	4	Good
16.		2	Poor	4	Good
17.		1	Very Poor	4	Good
18.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
19.		3	Average	5	Very Good
20.		1	Very Poor	3	Average
21.		3	Average	5	Very Good
22.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
23.		3	Average	5	Very Good
24.		2	Poor	4	Good
25.		4	Good	6	Excellent
26.		3	Average	5	Very Good
27.		2	Poor	4	Good
28.		4	Good	5	Very Good
29.		3	Average	4	Good
30.		3	Average	5	Very Good
31.		4	Good	5	Very Good
32.		1	Very Poor	4	Good
33.		3	Average	6	Excellent
Total		88		155	

Appendix B

Experimental Class

The classification of the students' Fluency in pre test and post test

No.	Sample	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Score	Classification	Score	Classification
1.		3	Average	6	Excellent
2.		4	Good	5	Very Good
3.		4	Good	6	Excellent
4.		3	Average	4	Good
5.		4	Good	5	Very Good
6.		4	Good	5	Very Good
7.		3	Average	4	Good
8.		2	Poor	4	Good
9.		3	Average	5	Very Good
10.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
11.		3	Average	6	Excellent
12.		4	Good	6	Excellent
13.		3	Average	4	Good
14.		3	Average	4	Good
15.		2	Poor	4	Good
16.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
17.		3	Average	4	Good
18.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
19.		3	Average	4	Good
20.		2	Poor	3	
21.		3	Average	5	Very Good
22.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
23.		3	Average	4	Good
24.		4	Good	6	Excellent
25.		3	Average	5	Very Good
26.		3	Average	5	Very Good
27.		3	Average	4	Good
28.		4	Good	5	Very Good
29.		3	Average	4	Good
30.		3	Average	5	Very Good
31.		4	Good	6	Excellent
32.		1	Very Poor	4	Good
33.		4	Good	5	Very Good
Total		99		157	

Appendix C

Experimental Class

The classification of the students' Comprehensibility in pre-test and post-test

No.	Sample	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Score	Classification	Score	Classification
1.		3	Average	6	Excellent
2.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
3.		3	Average	5	Very Good
4.		3	Average	4	Good
5.		4	Good	6	Excellent
6.		5	Very Good	5	Very Good
7.		3	Average	4	Good
8.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
9.		3	Average	6	Excellent
10.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
11.		2	Poor	4	Good
12.		3	Average	5	Very Good
13.		2	Poor	4	Good
14.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
15.		2	Poor	4	Good
16.		3	Average	5	Very Good
17.		3	Average	4	Good
18.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
19.		3	Average	4	Good
20.		2	Poor	3	Average
21.		2	Poor	3	Average
22.		2	Poor	4	Good
23.		3	Average	4	Good
24.		3	Average	5	Very Good
25.		3	Average	6	Excellent
26.		3	Average	5	Very Good
27.		3	Average	4	Good
28.		4	Good	5	Very Good
29.		3	Average	4	Good
30.		3	Average	5	Very Good
31.		4	Good	5	Very Good
32.		1	Very Poor	4	Good
33.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
Total		90		153	

Appendix D

Control Class

The classification of the students' Accuracy in pre test and post test

No.	Sample	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Score	Classification	Score	Classification
1.		3	Average	4	Good
2.		2	Poor	4	Good
3.		2	Poor	4	Good
4.		1	Very Poor	3	Average
5.		1	Very Poor	3	Average
6.		3	Average	4	Good
7.		2	Poor	3	Average
8.		2	Poor	3	Average
9.		2	Poor	3	Average
10.		3	Average	4	Good
11.		2	Poor	4	Good
12.		2	Poor	4	Good
13.		1	Very Poor	3	Average
14.		2	Poor	4	Good
15.		1	Very Poor	3	Average
16.		2	Poor	3	Average
17.		2	Poor	4	Good
18.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
19.		3	Average	6	Excellent
20.		1	Very Poor	3	Average
21.		2	Poor	4	Good
22.		2	Poor	4	Good
23.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
24.		2	Poor	4	Good
25.		3	Average	5	Very Good
26.		3	Average	4	Good
27.		2	Poor	4	Good
28.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
29.		2	Poor	4	Good
30.		3	Average	4	Good
31.		2	Poor	4	Good
32.		1	Very Poor	3	Average
Total		65		124	

Appendix E

Control Class

The classification of the students' Fluency in pre test and post test

No.	Sample	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Score	Classification	Score	Classification
1.		3	Average	4	Good
2.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
3.		4	Good	5	Very Good
4.		2	Poor	3	Average
5.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
6.		3	Average	5	Very Good
7.		1	Very Poor	3	Average
8.		1	Very Poor	3	Average
9.		3	Average	3	Average
10.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
11.		3	Average	4	Good
12.		2	Poor	3	Average
13.		3	Average	4	Good
14.		1	Very Poor	3	Average
15.		2	Poor	4	Good
16.		2	Poor	3	Average
17.		3	Average	4	Good
18.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
19.		3	Average	4	Good
20.		2	Poor	3	Average
21.		2	Poor	4	Good
22.		2	Poor	3	Average
23.		3	Average	3	Average
24.		3	Average	4	Good
25.		2	Poor	3	Average
26.		2	Poor	3	Average
27.		3	Average	3	Average
28.		3	Average	4	Good
29.		2	Poor	4	Good
30.		3	Average	4	Good
31.		4	Good	5	Very Good
32.		1	Very Poor	3	Average
Total		76		121	

Appendix F

Control Class

The classification of the students' Comprehensibility in pre-test and post-test

No.	Sample	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Score	Classification	Score	Classification
1.		2	Poor	4	Good
2.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
3.		1	Very Poor	4	Good
4.		3	Average	4	Good
5.		3	Average	5	Very Good
6.		3	Average	5	Very Good
7.		4	Good	5	Very Good
8.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
9.		3	Average	6	Excellent
10.		2	Poor	4	Good
11.		1	Very Poor	4	Good
12.		3	Average	5	Very Good
13.		3	Average	4	Good
14.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
15.		2	Poor	4	Good
16.		3	Average	5	Very Good
17.		3	Average	4	Good
18.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
19.		3	Average	4	Good
20.		2	Poor	3	Average
21.		2	Poor	3	Average
22.		2	Poor	4	Good
23.		2	Poor	4	Good
24.		3	Average	6	Excellent
25.		3	Average	5	Very Good
26.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
27.		3	Average	4	Good
28.		4	Good	5	Very Good
29.		3	Average	4	Good
30.		3	Average	5	Very Good
31.		3	Average	4	Good
32.		1	Very Poor	4	Good
Total		80		143	

Appendix G

Experimental Class

The classification of the students' Speaking Ability (Final Score) in pre-test and post-test

No.	Sample	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Score	Classification	Score	Classification
1.		3.33	Average	5.67	Very Good
2.		3	Average	5	Very Good
3.		3	Average	5.33	Very Good
4.		2.67	Poor	4	Good
5.		3	Average	4.67	Good
6.		4	Good	5	Very Good
7.		3	Average	4	Good
8.		2	Poor	4.33	Good
9.		3	Average	5.33	Very Good
10.		2.33	Poor	5.33	Very Good
11.		3	Average	5.67	Very Good
12.		3.67	Average	5.67	Very Good
13.		2.67	Poor	4.33	Good
14.		2.67	Poor	4.33	Good
15.		2	Poor	4	Good
16.		2.33	Poor	4.67	Good
17.		2.33	Poor	4	Good
18.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
19.		3	Average	4.33	Good
20.		1.67	Very Poor	3	Average
21.		2.67	Poor	4.33	Good
22.		2	Poor	4.67	Good
23.		3	Average	4.33	Good
24.		3	Average	5	Very Good
25.		3.33	Average	5.67	Very Good
26.		3	Average	5	Very Good
27.		2.67	Poor	4	Good
28.		4	Good	5	Very Good
29.		3	Average	4	Good
30.		3	Average	5	Very Good
31.		4	Good	5.33	Very Good
32.		1	Very Poor	4	Good
33.		3	Average	5.33	Very Good
Total		60		66	

Appendix H

Control Class

The classification of the students' Speaking Ability (Final Score) in pre-test and post-test

No.	Sample	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Score	Classification	Score	Classification
1.		2.67	Poor	4	Good
2.		2	Poor	4.67	Good
3.		2.33	Poor	4.33	Good
4.		2	Poor	3.33	Average
5.		2	Poor	4.33	Good
6.		3	Average	4.67	Good
7.		2.33	Poor	3.67	Average
8.		1.67	Very Poor	3.67	Average
9.		2.67	Poor	4	Good
10.		2.33	Poor	4.33	Good
11.		2	Poor	4	Good
12.		2.33	Poor	4	Good
13.		2.33	Poor	3.67	Average
14.		1.67	Very Poor	4	Good
15.		1.67	Very Poor	3.67	Average
16.		2.33	Poor	3.67	Average
17.		2.67	Poor	4	Good
18.		2	Poor	5	Very Good
19.		3	Average	4.67	Good
20.		1.67	Very Poor	3	Average
21.		2	Poor	3.67	Average
22.		2	Poor	3.67	Average
23.		2.33	Poor	4	Good
24.		2.67	Poor	4.67	Good
25.		2.67	Poor	4.33	Good
26.		2.33	Poor	4	Good
27.		2.67	Poor	3.67	Average
28.		3	Average	4.67	Good
29.		2.33	Poor	4	Good
30.		3	Average	4.33	Good
31.		3	Average	4.33	Good
32.		1	Very Poor	3.33	Average
Total		30		40	

Appendix M
Experimental Class
Rating score of students' Accuracy in Pre-test and Post-test

Sample	Pre-test		Post-test		Gain	D^2
	X_1	X_1^2	X_2	X_2^2	$D(X_2 - X_1)$	
1.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
2.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
3.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
4.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
5.	1.67	2.79	5	25	3.33	11.09
6.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
7.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
8.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
9.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
10.	5	25	10	100	5	25
11.	6.67	44.49	10	100	3.33	11.09
12.	6.67	44.49	10	100	3.33	11.09
13.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
14.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
15.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
16.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
17.	1.67	2.79	6.67	44.49	5	25
18.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
19.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
20.	1.67	2.79	5	25	3.33	11.09
21.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
22.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
23.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
24.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
25.	6.67	44.49	10	100	3.33	11.09
26.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
27.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
28.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
29.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
30.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
31.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
32.	1.67	2.79	6.67	44.49	5	25
33.	5	25	10	100	5	25
Total	$\sum X_1$ = 146.67	$\sum X_1^2$ = 727.91	$\sum X_2$ = 258.32	$\sum X_2^2$ = 2080.24	$\sum D$ = 111.65	$\sum D^2$ = 413.87

Appendix N
Experimental Class
Rating score of students' Fluency in Pre-test and Post-test

Sample	Pre-test		Post-test		Gain	D^2
	X_1	X_1^2	X_2	X_2^2	$D(X_2 - X_1)$	
1.	5	25	10	100	5	25
2.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
3.	6.67	44.49	10	100	3.33	11.09
4.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
5.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
6.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
7.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
8.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
9.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
10.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
11.	5	25	10	100	5	25
12.	6.67	44.49	10	100	3.33	11.09
13.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
14.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
15.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
16.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
17.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
18.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
19.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
20.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
21.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
22.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
23.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
24.	6.67	44.49	10	100	3.33	11.09
25.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
26.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
27.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
28.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
29.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
30.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
31.	6.67	44.49	10	100	3.33	11.09
32.	1.67	2.79	6.67	44.49	5	25
33.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
Total	$\sum X_1$ = 165.01	$\sum X_1^2$ = 880.83	$\sum X_2$ = 261.66	$\sum X_2^2$ = 2130.34	$\sum D$ = 96.65	$\sum D^2$ = 338.83

Appendix O
Experimental Class
Rating score of students' Comprehensibility in Pre-test and Post-test

Sample	Pre-test		Post-test		Gain	D^2
	X_1	X_1^2	X_2	X_2^2	$D(X_2 - X_1)$	
1.	5	25	10	100	5	25
2.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
3.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
4.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
5.	6.67	44.49	10	100	3.33	11.09
6.	8.33	69.39	8.33	69.39	0	1
7.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
8.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
9.	5	25	10	100	5	25
10.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
11.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
12.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
13.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
14.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
15.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
16.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
17.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
18.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
19.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
20.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
21.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
22.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
23.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
24.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
25.	5	25	10	100	5	25
26.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
27.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
28.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
29.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
30.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
31.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
32.	1.67	2.79	6.67	44.49	5	25
33.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
Total	$\sum X_1$ = 149.97	$\sum X_1^2$ = 738.73	$\sum X_2$ = 254.99	$\sum X_2^2$ = 2024.73	$\sum D$ = 105.02	$\sum D^2$ = 403.9

Appendix P
Experimental Class

Rating score of students' Speaking ability (Final Score) in Pre-test and Post-test

Sample	Pre-test		Post-test		Gain	D^2
	X_1	X_1^2	X_2	X_2^2	$D(X_2 - X_1)$	
1.	5.55	30.85	9.45	89.35	3.90	15.21
2.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
3.	5	25	8.88	78.84	3.88	15.04
4.	4.45	19.85	6.67	44.49	29.62	877.34
5.	5	25	7.78	60.54	2.78	7.74
6.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
7.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.76
8.	3.33	11.09	7.22	52.14	2.18	4.74
9.	5	25	8.88	78.84	3.88	15.04
10.	3.88	15.04	8.88	78.84	5	25
11.	5	25	9.45	89.35	4.45	19.85
12.	6.11	37.31	9.45	89.35	3.34	11.16
13.	4.45	19.85	7.22	52.14	2.77	7.69
14.	4.45	19.85	7.22	52.14	2.77	7.69
15.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
16.	3.88	15.04	7.78	60.54	3.90	15.21
17.	3.88	15.04	6.67	44.49	2.79	7.71
18.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
19.	5	25	7.22	52.14	2.22	4.94
20.	2.78	7.74	5	25	2.22	4.94
21.	4.45	19.85	7.22	52.14	2.77	7.69
22.	3.33	11.09	7.78	60.54	4.45	19.85
23.	5	25	7.22	52.14	2.22	4.94
24.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
25.	5.55	30.85	9.45	89.35	3.90	15.21
26.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
27.	4.45	19.85	6.67	44.49	2.22	4.94
28.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
29.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
30.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
31.	6.67	44.49	8.88	78.84	2.21	4.81
32.	1.67	2.79	6.67	44.49	5	25
33.	5	25	8.88	78.84	3.33	11.09
Total	$\sum X_1$ = 153.88	$\sum X_1^2$ = 756.74	$\sum X_2$ = 258.86	$\sum X_2^2$ = 2068.22	$\sum D$ = 130.12	$\sum D^2$ = 1224.42

Appendix P
Control Class

Rating score of students' Accuracy in Pre-test and Post-test

Sample	Pre-test		Post-test		Gain	D^2
	X_1	X_1^2	X_2	X_2^2	$D(X_2 - X_1)$	
1.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
2.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
3.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
4.	1.67	2.79	5	25	3.33	11.09
5.	1.67	2.79	5	25	3.33	11.09
6.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
7.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
8.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
9.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
10.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
11.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
12.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
13.	1.67	2.79	5	25	3.33	11.09
14.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
15.	1.67	2.79	5	25	3.33	11.09
16.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
17.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
18.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
19.	5	25	10	100	5	25
20.	1.67	2.79	5	25	3.33	11.09
21.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
22.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
23.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
24.	3.33	11.9	6.67	44.49	33.34	11.16
25.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
26.	5	25	6.67	44.40	1.67	2.79
27.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
28.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
29.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
30.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
31.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
32.	1.67	2.79	5	25	5	25
Total	$\sum X_1$ = 108.29	$\sum X_1^2$ = 403.26	$\sum X_2$ = 206.71	$\sum X_2^2$ = 1383.8	$\sum D$ = 130.09	$\sum D^2$ = 350.57

Appendix Q
Control Class

Rating score of students' Fluency in Pre-test and Post-test

Sample	Pre-test		Post-test		Gain	D^2
	X_1	X_1^2	X_2	X_2^2	$D(X_2 - X_1)$	
1.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
2.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
3.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
4.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
5.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
6.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
7.	1.67	2.79	5	25	3.33	11.09
8.	1.67	2.79	5	25	3.33	11.09
9.	5	25	5	25	0	1
10.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
11.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
12.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
13.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
14.	1.67	2.79	5	25	3.33	11.09
15.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
16.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
17.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
18.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
19.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
20.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
21.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
22.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
23.	5	25	5	25	0	1
24.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
25.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
26.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
27.	5	25	5	25	0	1
28.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
29.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
30.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
31.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
32.	1.67	2.79	5	25	3.33	11.09
Total	$\sum X_1$ = 126.64	$\sum X_1^2$ = 555.4	$\sum X_2$ = 201.68	$\sum X_2^2$ = 1325.12	$\sum D$ = 75.04	$\sum D^2$ = 239.3

**Appendix Q
Control Class**

Rating score of students' Comprehensibility in Pre-test and Post-test

Sample	Pre-test		Post-test		Gain	D^2
	X_1	X_1^2	X_2	X_2^2	$D(X_2 - X_1)$	
1.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
2.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
3.	1.67	2.79	6.67	44.49	5	25
4.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
5.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
6.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
7.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
8.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
9.	5	25	10	100	5	25
10.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
11.	1.67	2.79	6.67	44.49	5	25
12.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
13.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
14.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
15.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
16.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
17.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
18.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
19.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
20.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
21.	3.33	11.09	5	25	1.67	2.79
22.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
23.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
24.	5	25	10	100	5	25
25.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
26.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
27.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
28.	6.67	44.49	8.33	69.39	1.66	2.76
29.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
30.	5	25	8.33	69.39	3.33	11.09
31.	5	25	6.67	44.49	1.67	2.79
32.	1.67	2.79	6.67	44.49	5	25
Total	$\sum X_1$ = 133.31	$\sum X_1^2$ = 605.43	$\sum X_2$ = 238.34	$\sum X_2^2$ = 1819.42	$\sum D$ = 105.03	$\sum D^2$ = 402.97

Appendix R
Control Class

Rating score of students' Speaking ability (Final Score) in Pre-test and Post-test

Sample	Pre-test		Post-test		Gain	D^2
	X_1	X_1^2	X_2	X_2^2	$D(X_2 - X_1)$	
1.	4.45	19.85	6.67	44.49	2.22	4.94
2.	3.33	11.09	7.78	60.54	4.45	19.85
3.	3.88	15.04	7.22	52.14	3.34	11.16
4.	3.33	11.09	5.55	30.85	2.22	4.94
5.	3.33	11.09	7.22	52.14	3.89	15.13
6.	5	25	7.78	60.54	2.78	7.74
7.	3.88	15.04	6.17	38.09	2.29	5.21
8.	2.78	7.74	6.17	38.09	3.39	11.41
9.	4.45	19.85	6.67	44.49	2.22	4.94
10.	3.88	15.04	7.22	52.14	3.34	11.16
11.	3.33	11.09	6.67	44.49	3.34	11.16
12.	3.88	15.04	6.67	44.49	2.79	7.71
13.	3.88	15.04	6.17	38.09	2.79	7.71
14.	2.78	7.74	6.67	44.49	3.89	15.13
15.	2.78	7.74	6.17	38.09	3.39	11.41
16.	3.88	15.04	6.17	38.09	2.79	7.71
17.	4.45	19.85	6.67	44.49	2.22	4.94
18.	3.33	11.09	8.33	69.39	5	25
19.	5	25	7.78	60.54	2.78	7.74
20.	2.78	7.74	5	25	2.22	4.94
21.	3.33	11.09	6.17	38.09	3.34	11.16
22.	3.33	11.09	6.17	38.09	2.84	8.06
23.	3.88	15.04	6.67	44.49	2.79	7.71
24.	4.45	19.85	7.78	60.54	3.33	11.09
25.	4.45	19.85	7.22	52.14	2.77	7.69
26.	3.88	15.04	6.67	44.49	2.79	7.71
27.	4.45	19.85	6.17	38.09	1.72	2.94
28.	5	25	7.78	60.54	2.78	7.74
29.	3.88	15.04	6.67	44.49	2.79	7.71
30.	5	25	7.22	52.14	2.22	4.94
31.	5	25	7.22	52.14	2.22	4.94
32.	1.67	2.79	5.55	30.85	3.88	15.04
Total	$\sum X_1$ = 122.72	$\sum X_1^2$ = 490.84	$\sum X_2$ = 216.04	$\sum X_2^2$ = 1476.76	$\sum D$ = 94.82	$\sum D^2$ = 296.66

Appendix S
Experiment Class

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Mean score and standard deviation of the students pre-test and post-test.

1. Accuracy

a) Mean score of pre-test

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{\sum X_1}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{146.67}{33}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = 4.45$$

b) Mean score of post-test

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{\sum X_2}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{258.32}{33}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = 7.87$$

c) Standard Deviation of pre-test
post-test

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{727.91 - \frac{(146.67)^2}{33}}{33-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{727.91 - 651.88}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{76.03}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{2.37}$$

$$SD = 1.53$$

d) Standard Deviation of

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{2080.24 - \frac{(258.32)^2}{33}}{33-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{2080.24 - 2022.09}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{58.15}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1.81}$$

$$SD = 1.34$$

2. Fluency

a) Mean score of pre-test

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{\sum X_1}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{165.01}{33}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = 5.03$$

c) Standard Deviation of pre-test post-test

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{880.83 - \frac{(165.01)^2}{33}}{33-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{880.83 - 825.1}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{55.73}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1.74}$$

$$SD = 1.32$$

b) Mean score of post-test

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{\sum X_2}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{261.66}{33}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = 7.92$$

d) Standard Deviation of

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{2130.34 - \frac{(261.66)^2}{33}}{33-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{2130.34 - 2074.72}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{58.15}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1.73}$$

$$SD = 1.31$$

3. Comprehensibility

a) Mean score of pre-test

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{\sum X_1}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{149.97}{33}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = 4.54$$

c) Standard Deviation of pre-test post-test

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{738.73 - \frac{(149.97)^2}{33}}{33-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{738.73 - 681.54}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{57.19}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1.78}$$

$$SD = 1.33$$

b) Mean score of post-test

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{\sum X_2}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{254.99}{33}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = 7.72$$

d) Standard Deviation of

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{2024.73 - \frac{(254.99)^2}{33}}{33-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{2024.73 - 1970.3}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{54.43}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1.70}$$

$$SD = 1.30$$

4. Speaking Ability (Final Score)

a) Mean score of pre-test

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{\sum X_1}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{153,88}{33}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = 4.66$$

c) Standard Deviation of pre-test post-test

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{756,74 - \frac{(153,88)^2}{33}}{33-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{756,74 - 717,54}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{39,2}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1,22}$$

$$SD = 1.10$$

b) Mean score of post-test

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{\sum X_2}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{258,86}{33}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = 7.84$$

d) Standard Deviation of

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{2068,22 - \frac{(258,86)^2}{33}}{33-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{2068,22 - 2030,56}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{37,66}{32}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1,17}$$

$$SD = 1.08$$

Appendix T

Control Class

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Mean score and standard deviation of the students pre-test and post-test.

1. Accuracy

a) Mean score of pre-test

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{\sum X_1}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{108.29}{32}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = 3.38$$

b) Mean score of post-test

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{\sum X_2}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{206.71}{32}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = 6.45$$

c) Standard Deviation of pre-test
post-test

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{403.26 - \frac{(108.29)^2}{32}}{32-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{403.26 - 366.46}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{36.8}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1.18}$$

$$SD = 1.08$$

d) Standard Deviation of

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{1383.8 - \frac{(206.71)^2}{32}}{32-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{1383.8 - 1335.28}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{48.52}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1.56}$$

$$SD = 1.24$$

2. Fluency

a) Mean score of pre-test

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{\sum X_1}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{126.64}{32}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = 3.95$$

c) Standard Deviation of pre-test
post-test

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{555.4 - \frac{(126.64)^2}{32}}{32-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{555.4 - 501.17}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{54.23}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1.74}$$

$$SD = 1.32$$

b) Mean score of post-test

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{\sum X_2}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{201.68}{32}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = 6.30$$

d) Standard Deviation of

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{1325.12 - \frac{(201.68)^2}{32}}{32-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{1325.12 - 1271.08}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{54.04}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1.73}$$

$$SD = 1.31$$

3. Comprehensibility

a) Mean score of pre-test

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{\sum X_1}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{133.31}{32}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = 4.16$$

c) Standard Deviation of pre-test
post-test

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{605.43 - \frac{(133.31)^2}{32}}{32-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{605.43 - 555.36}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{50.07}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1.61}$$

$$SD = 1.26$$

b) Mean score of post-test

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{\sum X_2}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{238.34}{32}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = 7.44$$

d) Standard Deviation of

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{1819.42 - \frac{(238.34)^2}{32}}{32-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{1819.42 - 1775.18}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{44.24}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{1.42}$$

$$SD = 1.19$$

4. Speaking Ability (Final Score)

a) Mean score of pre-test

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{\sum X_1}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = \frac{122,72}{32}$$

$$\bar{x}_1 = 4,83$$

c) Standard Deviation of pre-test
post-test

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{490,84 - \frac{(122,72)^2}{32}}{32-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{490,84 - 470,63}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{21,21}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{0,65}$$

$$SD = 0,85$$

b) Mean score of post-test

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{\sum X_2}{N}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = \frac{216,04}{32}$$

$$\bar{x}_2 = 6,75$$

d) Standard Deviation of

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{N}}{N-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{1476,76 - \frac{(216,04)^2}{32}}{32-1}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{1476,76 - 1458,54}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{18,22}{31}}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{0,58}$$

$$SD = 0,76$$

Calculating T-test

1. Experimental Class

a. Accuracy

$$\bar{D} = \frac{\sum D}{N} = \frac{111,65}{33} = 3,38$$

$$t = \frac{D}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 - \frac{(\sum D)^2}{N}}{N(N-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,38}{\sqrt{\frac{413,87 - \frac{(111,65)^2}{33}}{33(33-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,38}{\sqrt{\frac{413,87 - \frac{12465,72}{33}}{33(32)}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,38}{\sqrt{\frac{413,87 - 377,74}{1056}}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,38}{\sqrt{\frac{36,13}{1056}}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,38}{\sqrt{0,03}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,38}{0,17}$$

$$t = 19,88$$

b. Fluency

$$\bar{D} = \frac{\sum D}{N} = \frac{96,65}{33} = 2,92$$

$$t = \frac{D}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 - \frac{(\sum D)^2}{N}}{N(N-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,92}{\sqrt{\frac{338,83 - \frac{(96,65)^2}{33}}{33(33-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,92}{\sqrt{\frac{338,83 - \frac{9341,22}{33}}{33(32)}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,92}{\sqrt{\frac{338,83 - 283,06}{1056}}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,92}{\sqrt{\frac{55,7}{1056}}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,92}{\sqrt{0,05}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,92}{0,22}$$

$$t = 13,27$$

c. Comprehensibility

$$\bar{D} = \frac{\sum D}{N} = \frac{105,02}{33} = 3,18$$

$$t = \frac{D}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 - \frac{(\sum D)^2}{N}}{N(N-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,18}{\sqrt{\frac{403,9 - \frac{(105,02)^2}{33}}{33(33-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,18}{\sqrt{\frac{403,9 - \frac{11029,2}{33}}{33(32)}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,18}{\sqrt{\frac{403,9 - 334,21}{1056}}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,18}{\sqrt{\frac{69,69}{1056}}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,18}{\sqrt{0,06}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,18}{0,24}$$

$$t = 13,25$$

d. Speaking Ability

$$\bar{D} = \frac{\sum D}{N} = \frac{130,12}{33} = 3,94$$

$$t = \frac{D}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 - \frac{(\sum D)^2}{N}}{N(N-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,94}{\sqrt{\frac{1224,42 - \frac{(130,12)^2}{33}}{33(33-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,94}{\sqrt{\frac{1224,42 - \frac{16931,21}{33}}{33(32)}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,94}{\sqrt{\frac{1224,42 - 513,06}{1056}}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,94}{\sqrt{\frac{711,36}{1056}}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,94}{\sqrt{0,67}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,94}{0,81}$$

$$t = 4,86$$

2. Control Class

a. Accuracy

$$\bar{d} = \frac{\sum D}{N} = \frac{130,09}{32} = 4,06$$

$$t = \frac{D}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 - \frac{(\sum D)^2}{N}}{N(N-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{4,06}{\sqrt{\frac{350,57 - \frac{(130,09)^2}{32}}{32(32-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{4,06}{\sqrt{\frac{350,57 - \frac{16923,40}{32}}{32(31)}}$$

$$t = \frac{4,06}{\sqrt{\frac{350,57 - 528,85}{992}}$$

$$t = \frac{4,06}{\sqrt{\frac{-178,28}{992}}$$

$$t = \frac{4,06}{\sqrt{-0,17}}$$

$$t = \frac{4,06}{-0,41}$$

$$t = -3,65$$

b. Fluency

$$\bar{D} = \frac{\sum D}{N} = \frac{75,04}{32} = 2,34$$

$$t = \frac{D}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 - \frac{(\sum D)^2}{N}}{N(N-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,34}{\sqrt{\frac{239,3 - \frac{(75,04)^2}{32}}{32(32-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,34}{\sqrt{\frac{239,3 - \frac{5631,1}{32}}{32(31)}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,34}{\sqrt{\frac{239,3 - 175,97}{992}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,34}{\sqrt{\frac{63,33}{992}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,34}{\sqrt{0,06}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,34}{0,24}$$

$$t = 9,75$$

c. Comprehensibility

$$\bar{D} = \frac{\sum D}{N} = \frac{105,03}{32} = 3,28$$

$$t = \frac{D}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 - \frac{(\sum D)^2}{N}}{N(N-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,28}{\sqrt{\frac{402,97 - \frac{(105,03)^2}{32}}{32(32-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,28}{\sqrt{\frac{402,97 - \frac{11031,3}{32}}{32(31)}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,28}{\sqrt{\frac{402,97 - 334,72}{992}}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,28}{\sqrt{\frac{68,25}{992}}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,28}{\sqrt{0,06}}$$

$$t = \frac{3,28}{0,24}$$

$$t = 13,67$$

d. Speaking Ability

$$\bar{D} = \frac{\sum D}{N} = \frac{94,82}{32} = 2,96$$

$$t = \frac{D}{\sqrt{\frac{\sum D^2 - \frac{(\sum D)^2}{N}}{N(N-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,96}{\sqrt{\frac{296,66 - \frac{(94,82)^2}{32}}{32(32-1)}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,96}{\sqrt{\frac{296,66 - \frac{8990,83}{32}}{32(31)}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,96}{\sqrt{\frac{296,66 - 280,96}{992}}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,96}{\sqrt{\frac{15,7}{992}}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,96}{\sqrt{0,01}}$$

$$t = \frac{2,96}{0,1}$$

$$t = 29,6$$

ASPECT	CLASSIFICATION	SCORE	ANALYSIS
Accuracy	EXCELLENT	10	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She /ʃi:/, will /wil/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /in/, holiday /ˈhɒlədeɪ/, with /wiθ/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /ˈfæməli/</p>
		8,6	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She /ʃi:/, will /wil/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /in/, holiday /ˈhɒlədeɪ /, with /wit/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /ˈfæməli/</p>
	GOOD	8,5	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She /si:/, will /wil/, go /gɒ/, to /tu/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /in/, holiday /ˈhɒlideɪ/, with /wit/, her /he(r)/, family /ˈfæməli/</p>
		7,5	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She /si:/, will /wil/, go /gɒ/, to /tɒ/, the /də/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /in/, holiday /ˈhɒlideɪ/, with /wit/, her /he(r)/, family /ˈfamili/</p>
	POOR	5,1	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She /si:/, will /wil/, go /gɒ/, to /tɒ/, the /ðə/, beach /bich/, in /in/, holiday /ˈhɒlideɪ/, with /wit/, her /he(r)/, family /ˈfæməli/</p>
			<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She /si:/, will /wil/, go /gɒ/, to /tɒ/, the /də/, beach /bich/, in /in/, holiday /ˈhɒlideɪ/, with /wit/, her /he(r)/, family /ˈfæməli/</p>

	VERY POOR	4,0	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She /si:/, will /wil/, go /gO/, to /tO/, the /de/, beach /bich/, in /in/, holiday /'hOlidei/, with /wit/, her /he(r)/, family /'famili/</p>
Fluency	EXCELLENT	10	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She /ʃi:/, will /wil/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /in/, holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/, with /wiθ/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /'fæməli/</p>
		8,6	<p>“She will go to the beach with her family in holiday time”.</p> <p>She /ʃi:/, will /wil/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, with / wiθ/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /'fæməli/, in /in/, holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/, time /taɪm/</p>
	GOOD	8,5	<p>“She will go to the beach together with family”.</p> <p>She /si:/, will /wil/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /də/, beach /bi:tʃ/, together /tə'geðə(r)/, with / wiθ/, family /'fæməli/</p>
	POOR	5,1	<p>“She will go to at beach together family in time holiday”.</p> <p>She /si:/, will /wil/, go /go/, to /tu:/, at /et/, beach /bi:tʃ/, together /tʊgedə(r)/, family /'famili/, in /in/, time /taɪm/, holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/</p>
	VERY POOR	4,0	<p>“She will go to beach together family at time holiday”.</p> <p>She /si:/, will /wil/, go /go/, to /tu:/, beach /bich/, together</p>

			/tʊɡedə(r), family /'fæmɪli/, at /et/, time /tɑɪm/, holiday /'hɒlɪdeɪ/
Comprehensibility	EXCELLENT	10	“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”. She /ʃi:/, will /wɪl/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /ɪn/, holiday /'hɒlɪdeɪ/, with /wiθ/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /'fæməli/
	GOOD	8,6	“She will go to the beach with her family in holiday time”. She /ʃi:/, will /wɪl/, go /go/, to /tu:/, the /də/, beach /bi:tʃ/, with /wiθ/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /'fæməli/, in /ɪn/, holiday /'hɒlɪdeɪ/, time /tɑɪm/
	POOR	5,1	“She will goes to at beach with her family in holiday time”. She /ʃi:/, will /wɪl/, goes /gos/, to /tu:/, at /et/, beach /bɪtʃ/, with /wɪθ/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family /'fæməli/, in /ɪn/, holiday /'hɒlɪdeɪ/, time /tɑɪm/
	VERY POOR	4,0	“She will to goes to at beach together family at time holiday”. She /si:/, will /wɪl/, goes /gos/, to /tu:/, at /et/, beach /bɪtʃ/, together /tʊɡedə(r), family /'fæməli/, at /et/, time /tɑɪm/, holiday /hɒlɪdeɪ/
ACCENT	EXCELLENT	10	“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”. She /ʃi:/, will /wɪl/, go /gəʊ/, to /tu:/, the /ðə/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /ɪn/, holiday /'hɒlɪdeɪ/, with /wiθ/, her /hɜ:(r)/, family

			<i>/'fæməli/</i>
	GOOD	8,6	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She <i>/ʃi:/</i>, will <i>/wɪl/</i>, go <i>/ɡo/</i>, to <i>/tu:/</i>, the <i>/də/</i>, beach <i>/bi:tʃ/</i>, in <i>/ɪn/</i>, holiday <i>/'hɒlədeɪ/</i>, with <i>/wiθ/</i>, her <i>/hɜ:(r)/</i>, family <i>/'fæməli/</i></p>
	POOR	5,1	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She <i>/si:/</i>, will <i>/wɪl/</i>, go <i>/ɡo/</i>, to <i>/tu:/</i>, the <i>/de/</i>, beach <i>/bɪtʃ/</i>, in <i>/ɪn/</i>, holiday <i>/'hɒlədeɪ/</i>, with <i>/wɪt/</i>, (fillers eeee), her <i>/hɜ:(r)/</i>, family <i>/'fæməli/</i></p>
	VERY POOR	4,0	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She <i>/si:/</i>, will <i>/wɪl/</i>, go <i>/ɡəʊ/</i>, to <i>/tu:/</i>, the <i>/de/</i>, (fillers eeee), beach <i>/bi:tʃ/</i>, (fillers eeee), in <i>/ɪn/</i>, holiday <i>/'hɒlɪdeɪ/</i>, with <i>/wɪt/</i>, (fillers eeee), her <i>/he(r)/</i>, family <i>/'fæməli/</i></p>
EFFECTIVENESS	EXCELLENT	10	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She <i>/ʃi:/</i>, will <i>/wɪl/</i>, go <i>/ɡəʊ/</i>, to <i>/tu:/</i>, the <i>/ðə/</i>, beach <i>/bi:tʃ/</i>, in <i>/ɪn/</i>, holiday <i>/'hɒlədeɪ/</i>, with <i>/wiθ/</i>, her <i>/hɜ:(r)/</i>, family <i>/'fæməli/</i></p>
	GOOD	8,6	<p>“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”.</p> <p>She <i>/si:/</i>, will <i>/wɪl/</i>, go <i>/ɡəʊ/</i>, to <i>/tu:/</i>, the <i>/də/</i>, beach <i>/bi:tʃ/</i>, in</p>

			/in/ , holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/, with /wiθ/ , her /hɜ:(r)/, family /'fæməli/
	POOR	5,1	“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”. She /si:/, will /wil/, go /go/, to /tu/, the /de/, beach /bi:tʃ/, in /in/, holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/, (fillers eeee), with /wiθ/, (fillers eeee), her /hɜr/, family /'fæməli/
	VERY POOR	4,0	“She will go to the beach in holiday with her family”. She /si:/, will /wil/, go /go/, (fillers eeee), to /tu:/, the /de/, beach /bich/, (fillers eeee), in /in/, holiday /'hɒlədeɪ/, with /wit/, her /hɜr/, (fillers eeee), family /'famili/

Free Test of Experimental Class

Transcript 1

I think about ..e education is very important in our daily life, and then, in, in Indonesia I think is education is very bad because ..e is .. one of them in .. Indonesia system ..is very bad I think about examination final. Examination final is not fair for students because exak% examination final .. to make for student is stress and confuse about that, and automatically psy% physiology for students <@..> to make mm.. @ ... I think in my point of you aout ..e my plan in teacher mm I can to make in our .. e.. in my home village .. I can to make ... <@I can to make@> ..e cur% cursus.. what this? *Kurusus* kurs, curse <@ehh@> I think .. extracurricular is a ... is .. support our education.

Transcript 2

@I think education one of case in this country, why .. in every years in become ..e a one of problem .. like examination, its, its always become ..e trending topic, and I think is the ... e ..@ one of, one of ..problem ..e .. the government, government is not ..e is not professional for <@...@> the government @ is ..e not crucial for solve ..e that problem, I think that all.

Transcript 3

@pollution, <@I think@> I think about pollution is very bad for our healthy, why I say because ..e with pollution may be .. can make ..e emplacement lke that, .. and ..e influenza <@..@> and.. and I think we can we can make a definition about pollution, ..e may be we cannot many use a car or public transportation or motorcycle maybe and I think we can ..e we can use ..e bicycle ... e just now that ..a and <@we can use motorcycle@> and maybe ..e if you if we want ..e ..e going ..e going in other place we can ..e work, work, working, just that.

Transcript 4

In my mind, economic is case why the university students and the.. and the society make demonstration because they afraid, they can't to fulfill their need it because all of the need it has a price rise, and the one of ..e the case why the .. university and the society make ..e demonstration because their fu% their aspiration not hear by the government, thanks.

Transcript 5

I think the economic is very bad for ..e specially for society in Indonesia is very bad because why, we can see the hope from the government is not fear from the society in Indonesia, ..e there are many, poor in Indonesia can't get it, can't get the hope from the government, just ..e just the help just for the ..e rise the rise society, it's not it's not good because ..e the poor not ca% can to get their hope from the government and the government just not care about that just ..e in their ..e their system from the for the society is good but the application from the society is not good I think, thank you.

Post test of experimental class

Transcript 1

<@> Assalamu alykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu ..Thank you for the time giving to me to share to you all about my experience this one year have collage this Muhammadiyah University, including get one year I have ee good experience and bad experience. I will mention you all my good experience first, good is I have met with you all I mean what the pleasure for me such a good friends and kind like you all and, the second is I could rise up my religion knowledge in this Muhammadiyah university because this is a spy like religion of university and that all good experience. Now I want tell you about bad experience this university. The first one is very sad because the in the other university when the step up to the next semester is we change our classmate and I don't have problem with that, just problem is more you have known friends and connection in mean more good you are and the other is about the lecturers... because ee we are know that the lecture is usually late and including me also usually late but I am still a student it's ok for the lecturer. The other is the time of the time of we have learn is had to be late e don't that is to one think task to list I mean not very good for our e study stile. I think that all.

Transcript 2

Assalamualyikum warahmatullahi wabarakatu.

I want to tell about my experience English department English department. The first time study in English department I have problem, I can't speak English very well because my my skill in English ee past test but I am so give up, I always study and study to increase my speaking English e.. with e.. memorize vocabulary everyday and I practice with my face in glass and another people round me and I hope I can speak English very well .. in the future more better then today, thank you.

Transcript 3

Assalamu alykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu @ Ok, I have ee about reason why I choose English departemen ee..ee why I choose English department because ee .. ee English departemen is my favorite ee major, ee the second ee .. ia .. ee I am not diffikol (difficult) if I talk with a foreign ee with foreign ee so ee I must improve my e my skill ee in speaking ee, grammar, and pronunciation, I know my speak ee pronunciation, grammar, is very very wrong but I don't care – ee I don't care ee what say, ee what people say that for it. And .. I proper for my my self I ee I speak e ..

practice ..e practice by practice, so I so, if I e do it I think I will e I will a success woman, and I remember e my lacture e never said.. e if you e make mistake .. e is not problem.. e just e just speak up. Ee .. e mistain (mistake).. mistake e is the last .. and e I suggest ee to us, just speak up don't be don't be shy .. e .. w .. don't be shy e.. what people says to you. Ok I think there are there is a wide, there is a way. Ok I think is enough, thank you.

Transcript 4

Assalamualykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu<@...@> Ok I will talk about my lacture idol his name is Mattone @ .. He is..is very favourite ..e person to me because he always, he..he never come late to the class .. he was oldest but he..strong..he is very..his ..ever e.. angry to me because I come late but I enjoy because I will be angry to me ...one day..one day..I am forgot, I forgot to..to bring my assignment, and he..he angry to me. H was spurred..he was spurred..me because..because..he..never come late..and just one sentence.. I know about Sir Mattone..I..I am very..I am very far to Mr. Mattone. I think that all, Assalamualykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu.

Transcript 5

@Assalamualykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu. I want to explain my experience in English [department@..@](#). I am English department..I am very happy study to hard campus@ I am joint to EDSA English department students association..@ in EDSA I follow activity by EDSA English Camp. English camp in Pangkep Bontotallasa. English camp..e English camp come until five days .. this is the first time, I very happy because ..e @ I am very happy because ..e in there ..e I am with the all students EDSA, Thank you Assalamualykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu.

Free test For Control class

Transcript 1

Ok thank you, our Tim discuss about corruption specially in our country, ...am cross corruption is the one ..e works of the bad activity of government to take unresponsibly% irresponsible ..a the many of the people, so the effect of corrupt ..e make a poor or make a desirable ..e desirable condition of the people ..e especially in the poor ..e especially eco% ..e economic in the ..e people in thee people ..e who not to ..e get some good activity from the government so ..e what is the corruption? Corruption is the one activity of the government to should so bad ..e to make some a better life.

Transcript 2

..e I think corruption is very bad because ... e dipper economic the cityzem ... corruption ..e is political who lies public% the public and .. and very dangerous because ..e can get some people a sick or not happy because they can enjoy facility% the facility of the country, Ok thanks.

Transcript 3

..e my opinion about demonstration ..e positive effect, ..e demonstration. Sometime ..e demons% demonstration for men for infor% for their lie, the government is not to ... to.. to the <@ is not to@> to handle anything in good life, and although ... e although demonstration do it but government is not to hear it the activity ..and ...and ..e although so many people to say if ..e remonstrant% demonstrans..demonstrans is %apa% demonstrans .. to test% ..e to teas% to reside ..e image but ..e they can help ..e they can help ..e <@ the man for the society, I think hehe@>

Transcript 4

<@in my opinion about BLS@> I think if any BLS can make for society ..e additional poorman and helping for government can make the poor of society ..e should become about ite but there are% there are two effect for BLS, the fist ..ae negative, negative for BLS can make poor... can make of society lazy about is to work. And the positive effect can make ..e poor of society ... e.. can give ..e economic increase about that.

Transcript 5

The democracation in our country is very bad because is ..e because sometime gove% government ..e make ..e statement ..e which make the% of in this country is so..so no agree ..e with their ..e statement and ..a and when ..e when the this country if they man to choose the leader the many% many man this country not give the voice of the ..e their ..e their choose to be ..e to choose their leader, ..e and than ..e it so ..ee it so wrong because ..e everyone in this country must give ..e argument or ..e their statement ... e.. and make there are many people in this country not ..e not believe again with the ..e government <@ I think just all, thank you@>

Post test for control class

Transcript 1

@Assalamualykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu ..@..e Ok I want to explain, I want to talk about my experience in ..e English department When I ..e in English department I have many experience..one..e one of exper.. one,one of e experience e English..e English camp in the ..e.. Pangkep. ..e..English..English..English camp ..e give me many ..e.. give me many experience and I..I and I give them may friends to another class. Em..e.. why I choose English, English department because English ..e International branch and so..e I like it ..e English department because ..e English department is my favorite study, I think that' all, Assalamualykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu.

Transcript 2

@asslamualykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu. Thank you for the change. I went expel, I went ..e tell me about my experience @..Last time was studied in SMA 2 Bantaeng..I am happy because I have new friends.--when I start study in the class I am nerv%nerves because I cannot speak English but..teacher always ..e ..e study English, I think that all, assalamualykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu.

Transcript 3

<@assalamualykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu@><@ When I choce in..EDSA I am very happy@> follow..I follow activity...such as spending night, meeting club, and English camp.

Transcript 4

... Assalamualykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu..I would tell you, I would tell you about my experience, I registered English department, I have, much good experience while I study at this department. .. I met the new friends. They very good, smart, and careful. In my,in,in, in the classroom, they work activity. ^δ, Assalamu alykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu.

Transcript 5

<@Assalamuualykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu@>Thank for the change, Ok, I want to tell about my experience when I have study in English department ..e I was some special think I got in my life such ..e about in my cost, ..e about the lecturer, about new family, and about, about my friends and especially about ..e my way how to collage ..e in the way in the way like traffic jump ..I got, it was the big problem for me. Ok, ..e in English department .. in English department ..e I have got some, some lesson for me, like how life, how life without family and then how life own in this place and then how manage our time, how manage our time without our parents ..e in this house. Ok ..e the first%the first time when I ..e when I ..e in English department I have many friends, I talk she is my best friend but actually not, actually not, she was happy with other people..she was happy with other people, and than, ..e and than now I am two semesters, I hope, I hope the situation like this, the situation like this until finish in English department, that all.

Post-Test of control class

`Transcript 1

Thanks for the chance...from the university... one year... there are many of experience... like the positive and negative the system education in Muhammadiyah university.... Why I say the system education because there there are another schedule ... and then the system schedule up to balance the another university. Then eee I like Muhammadiyah university because eee there are many lecture give ee give ee learn for me ee and than eee Muhammadiyah university have ee there are many organization, thank you

Transcript 2

Ok aa I want to aa I want to tell my a experience in Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar. Before I study here I aaa I eee I came test in Universitas Negeri Makassar but I don't past the test and then I went to test in Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, and finally I I past test and now I am students in Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, I am choose English Departement especially is my mayor I proud the lecture in Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar especially lecture in English Departement. When I study in Muhammadiyah university I have many experience about looking in and I proud in Muhammadiyah university because Muhammadiyah university have many ee have many organization eee who have eeee one challenge in in the other regency or.... I think that all thank you

Transcript 3

I will tell my experience when I study in Muhammadiyah University. Actually this is my bad experience, I am very hate ee to the lecture who have lazy to go in the

campus to us eee material because the situation like that we have I have to sad see my friend who have ee back to home village only onece once time one years because they are so sad they eee missed her ee experience her ee her neighbor and the other, Ok I think that all thank you.

Transcript 4

Assalamualykum Warahmatullahi Wabaraku, Ok good afternoon everybody, e I just want to tell why I choose English Departement in here Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar because I think English Departement is very bare and English department with language ee English we can connect all people the world and ee I have had e that e limit your language is the limit your world, ok I think that all, thank you.

Transcript 5

Assalamualykum warahmatullahi wabarakatu, good afternoon everybody. Thanks for the change to me I wanna tell my experience for my study in here. I think at university of, I think at university of Muhammadiyah of Makassar there many e there are many organization in here, aa the one organization is very uniq for me is LKIM PENA but I don't join here last year because mmmm I a I don't know what is an LKIM PENA and than if I have come back my home village I hope ee I will to join in organization there and ee and ee and organization LKIM PENA is very interesting for me because my lacture is Mr. Arif is success full someone in organization there and I hope I can join in organization there and I like because in very like writing ee writing about my experience and my knowledge and ee some else, I think that all thank you very much.

Transcript 6

Asslm, thanks for the change, I want to tell about city Makassar, Makassar city ee ee I see Makassar city is ee very beautiful ammm I like the panorama I like the panorama aa Losari beach and And I aa and Makassar city is city metropolitan, I don't like aa Makssar city because is very hot and Makssar city is very danger and hot.

Transcript 7

Thanks for the change, I will tell about ee my experience sice I join in English department ee maybe ee I don't have a good skill in English but ee ee I I I I but since I join in English EDSA I have many experience especially ee ee if English department make an event ee ee maybe skill in English ee not increase but I have something special ee ee especially ee ee I get I I study how how how become a leader, I think that all thank you.

Transcript 8

Ok, thanks for the change for me, ee ee I will tell about ee University of Muhammadiyah Makassar in English department ee I think English Department ee is si good ee is for university and ee I think in English department for here because I want for speak English and I want master in speak English and English is international language and then I am very happy in there class room because I have eee I have many many friends mmm ann any progress ee for here ee Purnamayangsari Ok, Thank you.

Transcript 9

Thanks for the change given to me. I will tell about ee my experience in University Muhammadiyah Makassar. ..ee...when I ee study in University Muhammadiyah Makassar I am very happy because ee University Muhammadiyah Makassar at English department I can improve e speaking, reading, writing, pronunciation and listening, and in here I got many friends and and I proud the lactureof University Muhammadiyah Makassar.

Transcript 10

Ok, assalamualyikum warahmatullahi wabarakatu.... Thanks for the change for me em I feel very happy, very ee happy study in Muhammadiyah university of Makassar ee because ee I I got ee experience ee knowledge and my friends and very much my friends ee and and than ee I choose English department because e e actually e actually I don't like I don't like English and I donk know English but e I feel e English is the best for me e and e e I I don't likeI don't like when e I wedding e my lecture e but but e my lecture does doesn't e doesn't come in the in the campus, thank you.

